

**Assessment of the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits among Schoolchildren in Benin
City, Edo State.**

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DECLARATION

I now declare that this thesis is my original work except where otherwise acknowledged. It has neither been presented nor published anywhere else.

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to Nigeria, my fatherland, for being the comforting haven I proudly call home and the very framework upon which the core of my existence has taken shape. I also extend this dedication to all the conscientious Nigerians who ardently strive to advance the nation day by day.

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Osadolor Aisosa Junior

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

GSSH: Global School-based Student Health Survey

IQR: Inter-quartile range

LGA[s]: Local Government Area[s]

PSSS: Private Senior Secondary School

SCT: Social Cognitive Theory

SD: Standard Deviation

SES: Socio-economic status

WHO: World Health Organization

ABSTRACT

The global prevalence of oral diseases spans all age demographics and is intricately linked to individual oral hygiene practices. The formative years of schooling represent a critical period for children, where societal norms and habits are internalized; the deposition of positive habits during this developmental phase assures a secure oral health future. The present study aimed to evaluate the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

To achieve the study's aim, a sample of 424 schoolchildren from both public and private schools in Benin City, Edo State, was included, employing a multistage sampling technique. Data collection utilized a researcher-administered semi-structured questionnaire, and statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 25. Normality testing was performed through various methods, and descriptive statistics were presented using proportions, mean (SD), and median (IQR). Inferential analysis utilised non-parametric tests, including the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for bivariable association and a multinomial logistic regression for identifying the predictors of good and fair oral hygiene habits.

The study found that 19.3% of respondents exhibited poor oral hygiene habits, 68.8% displayed fair oral hygiene, and 11.8% demonstrated good oral hygiene practices. Additionally, 73.6% of respondents had never accessed dental services, with maternal influence being pivotal in shaping oral hygiene practices among respondents. Factors significantly associated with oral hygiene habits included age, school type, school location, parental education levels, household demographics, and gender ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, birth rank and family size showed non-significant associations ($p > 0.05$). Gender, age, and school location emerged as significant predictors of fair oral hygiene habits ($p < 0.05$), while parental education, school type, school location, and family structure predicted good oral hygiene habits ($p < 0.05$).

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The present inquiry's findings emphasize a notable prevalence of fair oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State, in relation to a limited utilization of dental services. Recommendations from the study include enhancing the capabilities of healthcare providers, particularly dental professionals, through targeted capacity-building. Additionally, escalating mass media campaigns and initiating school visits to raise awareness about oral health and promote healthy hygiene practices.

KEYWORDS: Assessment, Schoolchildren, Oral hygiene habits, Predictors, Benin City.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Children are individuals in the early stage of human development who have not yet attained adulthood, encompassing the childhood phase of life (Berk, 2018; Saavedra & Prentice, 2023). Childhood spans from birth to approximately twelve years of age; it is a crucial period marked by notable physical, cognitive, emotional, and social transformations (Berk, 2018). School-age [roughly between the ages of five and fifteen] is when children assimilate the societal norms and values necessary for becoming productive members (Ogordi et al., 2022; Saavedra & Prentice, 2023). Regrettably, many children in this age group still experience oral diseases due to insufficient oral hygiene habits (Ogordi et al., 2022).

Oral hygiene refers to practices that preserve the oral cavity's cleanliness and health by removing dental plaque and calculus from the tooth surfaces (Oyedele et al., 2019). Dental plaque represents a polymicrobial biofilm; in other words, a consortium of microbial cells residing within an extracellular matrix, thriving at the interface between two phases of matter (Valm, 2019). On the other hand, dental calculus, or *tartar*, as it is commonly called, is a calcified mass of dental plaque, usually found at intra-oral sites with a constant flow of saliva (Balaji et al., 2019). Insufficient oral hygiene and the accretion of dental plaque and calculus provide a habitat for harmful bacteria and their toxins, giving rise to various oral diseases, including dental caries, gingivitis, and periodontitis. Conversely, proper oral hygiene significantly reduces the buildup of dental plaque and calculus, promoting oral health and overall well-being while improving an individual's quality of life (Oyedele et al., 2019).

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As the saying goes, there is no smoke without fire; to have good oral hygiene, one must also have good habits. Habits are consistently repeated behavioural patterns, routines practised with frequency and presenting with considerable difficulty when attempting to halt (Chen et al., 2020). Predictors or factors, on the other hand, are measurable characteristics or attributes of an entity that can be used to forecast future events or outcomes in another entity based on presently known information (Kivelä et al., 2018). Parents play a significant role in children's acquisition of manifold societal norms and values, as children devote considerable time engaging with these family members, actively or passively imbibing their attitudes and practices (Nepaul & Mahomed, 2020). Parental factors such as age, knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning oral health, education level, and income level have been documented as notable predictors of a child's oral hygiene habits. (Ellakany et al., 2021; Nepaul & Mahomed, 2020; Oyedele et al., 2019; Pratamawari et al., 2022) Other oral hygiene habit predictors include a child's age and literacy level, birth rank, gender, and access to oral health educational resources (Oyedele et al., 2019; Shomuyiwa & Bridge, 2023).

1.1 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

Globally, the prevalence of untreated oral conditions rose from 2.5 billion individuals in 1990 to 3.5 billion in 2015, leading to a 64% increase in Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs); similarly, The Global Burden of Disease study (2010) reported an oral disease affectation of 3.9 billion people, conditions most of which were preventable [dental caries, and periodontal diseases] (Duangthip & Chu, 2020).

Regionally, reports from the World Health Organisation (WHO) Regional Office for Africa (2016) state that the prevalence of dental caries and periodontal diseases is rising, especially among children (Fomete & Adebayo, 2018).

In Nigeria, the scourge of preventable oral diseases is still palpable in the South-West, South-East, South-South, and North, with a dental caries prevalence of more than 12%, 30%, 10%, and 10%, respectively, and a significant presence of periodontal diseases. (Jibo & Mubarak, 2018; Igbinsosa et al., 2018; Okoli et al., 2021; Oyedele et al., 2021). These studies also affirmed the occurrence of these conditions amongst children with poorer oral hygiene status.

Oral hygiene has been established to be linked with oral diseases and non-communicable systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease, as both conditions share modifiable behavioural risk factors such as excess sugar consumption and unhealthy oral habits (Duangthip & Chu, 2020). Thus, good oral hygiene habits will help prevent oral diseases and eventually curtail some notable non-communicable systemic diseases. This study aims to bridge the existing gap in the literature by focusing on the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. While previous studies have provided valuable insights into the prevalence of oral conditions on a global, regional, and national scale, there is limited detailed investigation into the factors influencing oral hygiene practices, specifically among school-aged children nationally. By identifying and understanding these predictors, the research seeks to inform targeted interventions that can effectively improve oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren, ultimately contributing to the prevention of oral diseases and associated non-communicable systemic conditions.

1.2 AIM AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.2.1 AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aims to assess the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

1.2.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study focused on the following objectives to achieve the above aim.

1. To assess the levels of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.
2. To assess the level of utilisation of dental services among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.
3. To determine the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in public and private schools in Benin City, Edo State.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the levels of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State?
2. What is the level of dental services utilisation among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State?
3. What are the influences and predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in public and private schools in Benin City, Edo State?

1.4 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀ 1: Parental educational level is not a predictor of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

H₁ 1: Parental educational level is a predictor of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

H₀ 2: Predictors such as age, gender, number of children per household, family composition, school type, and school location are not significant predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

H1 2: Predictors such as age, gender, number of children per household, family composition, school type, and school location are significant predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

1. **Schoolchildren:** Understanding the predictors of oral hygiene habits can directly benefit schoolchildren by promoting better oral health practices. They will gain knowledge about maintaining proper oral hygiene, leading to healthier teeth and gums. This education can contribute to their overall well-being and self-confidence.

2. **Parents:** Parents play an indelible role in shaping their children's habits. Knowledge of the predictors of oral hygiene habits will enable parents to guide their children toward adopting good oral health practices from an early age; this can prevent dental issues and instil lifelong oral care habits.

3. **Learning institutions:** Schools can incorporate oral hygiene education into their curriculum, enhancing students' awareness and practices related to oral health; this can contribute to a healthier school environment and reduce absenteeism due to dental problems.

4. **Policy Makers:** The data on predictors of oral hygiene habits can inform policymakers about the importance of integrating oral health education into broader health and education policies. This move can lead to the development of targeted interventions and campaigns aimed at improving oral health outcomes among schoolchildren.

5. **Government:** Governments can use the insights from this research to design and implement effective oral health promotion programs; this can help reduce the burden of preventable oral diseases, leading to improved overall public health and well-being.

6. **Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):** NGOs focused on health and education can use the findings to design outreach programs and initiatives that specifically address oral health issues among schoolchildren; this can contribute to a more comprehensive approach to children's well-being.

7. **Specialized Institutions:** Institutions specializing in oral health research and education can use the data to enhance their educational programmes and provide evidence-based guidance to other stakeholders; this can ensure that their efforts are aligned with the most effective strategies.

8 **Future Researchers:** The investigation will contribute to the existing knowledge on oral hygiene predictors among schoolchildren. Future researchers can build upon this information, deepening our understanding of the factors influencing oral health habits and refining interventions.

9. **Reference for Data Collection:** The study will serve as a reference for researchers conducting similar studies in the future; this will aid in standardizing data collection methods and comparing results across different populations and contexts.

1.6 STUDY JUSTIFICATION

A literature search within the last ten years revealed limited information concerning the assessment of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren except for studies by Oyedele et al. (2019) and Lawal et al. (2022) in the South-West and Jibo and Mubarak (2018) in the North, no other Nigerian study within this timeframe focused on assessing the predictors of oral hygiene habits in schoolchildren, but instead on the oral hygiene status of schoolchildren. In addition, from my encounters with schoolchildren in my locality during oral health outreaches, I have noticed poor oral hygiene status among this population; thus, a desire to assess the predictors

of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren was birthed. Moreover, while Oyedele et al. (2019) explored the social predictors of oral hygiene, their focus was primarily on the oral hygiene status rather than the oral hygiene habits of schoolchildren. Conversely, Lawal et al. (2022) concentrated solely on investigating the impact of oral hygiene habits on health-related quality of life. Additionally, Jibo and Mubarak (2018) centred their study on assessing the knowledge and practice of oral hygiene. None of the above studies sought to discover dental service utilisation among schoolchildren; the present research seeks to address these critical gaps in the literature by explicitly investigating the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City. This study intends to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing oral hygiene practices, contributing valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge.

1.7 DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

Assessment: This is the process of evaluating or appraising the knowledge, skills, abilities, characteristics, or performance of individuals, groups, or entities.

Predictors: These are variables or factors that are used to forecast or anticipate a particular outcome or behaviour.

Oral hygiene habits: These are a set of regular practices and behaviours aimed at maintaining the cleanliness and health of the mouth, teeth, gums, and overall oral cavity.

Knowledge: This refers to the understanding, information, and awareness that an individual possesses about various facts, concepts, ideas, principles, experiences, or skills.

Dental service utilisation: This refers to the percentage of the population accessing dental services within a specified period

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Socioeconomic status (SES): This refers to an individual's or a family's social and economic position within a society. A combination of income, education level, occupation, and social standing determines it.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter was discussed under the following subheadings:

- Conceptual review
- Empirical studies
- Theoretical framework
- Summary of chapter

2.1 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Oral hygiene entails the disciplined maintenance of cleanliness within the oral cavity, with the sole aim of preventing oral diseases and related concerns such as bad breath (Janani et al., 2022).

The initiation of oral hygiene care for a child commences immediately after birth; parents are advised to wrap a moistened washcloth around their index finger and gently massage the gum pads, removing any residual debris from breastfeeding (New York State Department of Health, 2019). As the child reaches the sixth to eighth month, the appearance of the first teeth signals the commencement of toothbrushing; parents also play a pivotal role during this phase, using a soft-bristle toothbrush and a smear of toothpaste for the child's toothbrushing (New York State Department of Health, 2019).

Parents who remain responsible for their child's oral hygiene maintenance between twelve and eighteen months of age utilise a soft-bristle toothbrush and a pea-sized amount of toothpaste twice daily. All primary teeth typically emerge in the oral cavity between eighteen months and five years. By the age of two, children are taught to spit out the lather from the toothpaste during toothbrushing

while being closely monitored to ensure it is not swallowed. During this stage, parents or guardians guide the child in toothbrushing until they develop manual dexterity to clean their teeth better (New York State Department of Health, 2019).

In view of the appropriate maintenance of oral hygiene in children, the choice of a suitable toothbrush is crucial. Soft bristles are essential for a gentle approach, considering the sensitivity of a child's oral tissues. The toothbrush should feature a small head to adapt effectively to the child's oral anatomy, with a curved design to prevent injuries in the retromolar area (Atarbashi-Moghadam & Atarbashi-Moghadam, 2018). The handle design is also essential; optimal handling is achieved through a shorter handle with a rough texture, facilitating a secure grip for the child (Atarbashi-Moghadam & Atarbashi-Moghadam, 2018).

The toothbrushing procedure involves the following:

- Moisten the toothbrush bristles with water before applying pea-sized toothpaste.
- Hold the toothbrush perpendicular to the tooth surfaces.
 - Horizontal scrub technique: Use gentle, back-and-forth motion to clean the outer and inner tooth surfaces, paying attention to the gum line. Clean the chewing surfaces with back-and-forth or up-and-down motions.
 - Fones technique: Use gentle circular motions, clean the inner and outer surfaces, and pay attention to the gum line. Clean the chewing surfaces with back-and-forth or up-and-down motions.
- Gently brush the tongue's surface to remove bacteria and freshen the breath.
- Brush for at least two minutes for thorough cleaning.

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- Spit out excess toothpaste; avoid rinsing immediately to allow fluoride to continue protecting the teeth.
- Brush at least twice a day, preferably in the morning after breakfast and before bedtime.
- After use, place the toothbrush in an aerated location with the bristles facing upwards to promote proper drying and prevent moisture accumulation.
- Replace the toothbrush every three to four months or sooner if the bristles are frayed.
- Floss between teeth daily.

Unsupervised brushing is generally feasible by the age of six or seven. From ages six through ten, the child is also taught how to use a piece of dental floss; the parent begins the procedure, flossing the child once daily; subsequently, the child is to model the parent until mastery is achieved. Children should brush their teeth for at least two to three minutes, at least twice a day, using a pea-sized amount of fluoridated toothpaste; this established routine contributes to optimal oral health during the formative years (New York State Department of Health, 2019).

Figure 1: A photograph showing the toothbrushes of children.

Source: Glister <https://rb.gy/Orumi>

While the maintenance of oral hygiene has only benefits, not complications, the use of the toothbrush has been documented to be associated with the precipitation of some adverse events, such as toothbrush ingestion and toothbrush impaction, as reported in a systematic review by Olivera et al. (2014).

2.1.1.1 IMPORTANCE OF ORAL HYGIENE

According to the WHO (2017), hygiene refers to conditions and practices that help to maintain health and prevent the spread of diseases (Goryawala, 2018). Oral hygiene, as described by Bonetti et al. (2015), involves maintaining the health of the oral cavity by cleaning the gums, teeth, tongue, lips, and dentures, if applicable (Dagnew et al., 2020).

Oral hygiene can be maintained by daily [at least twice] toothbrushing using a soft to medium strength bristle toothbrush with a fluoride-containing toothpaste, the use of interdental cleaning aids such as dental floss, and the water floss [especially in young children] (Xu et al., 2023; Popescu et al., 2021). Furthermore, other methods of maintaining oral hygiene include using antibacterial mouthwash, paying regular visits to the dentist for check-ups and routine cleaning, and substituting highly cariogenic diets for fruits and sugarless alternatives (Popescu et al., 2021). Ensuring proper oral hygiene is essential not only for maintaining the freshness of the whole mouth all day but also for preventing the onset of oral diseases (Dagneu et al., 2020; Dhage & Chougule, 2019; Goryawala, 2018; Popescu et al., 2021), such as gingivitis, dental caries, periodontitis, and oral cancers (Hakeem et al., 2019). These previously stated oral diseases have been suggested to be linked with the onset of diseases in other parts of the body and the maintenance of general well-being. (Popescu et al., 2021).

2.1.1.2 PREVALENCE OF POOR ORAL HYGIENE AND ORAL DISEASE AMONG SCHOOLCHILDREN

Kier (2011) defined prevalence as the percentage of the population experiencing a particular condition either at a specific moment in time [point prevalence] or over a designated period [period prevalence] (Tenny & Hoffman, 2023). Schoolchildren refer to pupils or students who attend school and are typically in the age range of primary or secondary education (Nyatuka, 2020)

Globally, the prevalence of poor oral hygiene is still palpable, especially among lower-income populations. Pengpid and Peltzer (2020), in their ‘Global School-based Student Health Survey’ (GSHS) study, recorded a poor oral hygiene prevalence of approximately 17% among school adolescents in three Caribbean countries [Dominican Republic, Suriname, and Trinidad &

Tobago]. The findings by Pengpid and Peltzer (2020) were similar to that of a previously conducted GSHS study by McKittrick & Jacobsen (2015) among middle school students from fifteen Latin American and Caribbean countries [Antigua and Barbuda, Argentina, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Costa Rica, Grenada, Guatemala, Guyana, Peru, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and Grenadines, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, and Uruguay]. The study by McKittrick and Jacobsen (2015) reported a prevalence of poor oral hygiene across the countries, ranging from 2% to 7 % (Pengpid & Peltzer, 2020). Bardach et al. (2021), in their Mongolian GSHS study among schoolchildren aged 12 – 16, noticed a prevalence of 33% for poor oral hygiene. Meanwhile, Gebregiorgis et al. (2021) discovered a prevalence of 70% for poor oral hygiene among a population of middle school students in Eritrea.

Continentially, a systematic review and meta-analysis of forty-six studies conducted in East Africa between the year 2000 and the year 2020 among predominantly schoolchildren discovered that the prevalence of dental caries was above 45%, poor oral hygiene was considerably associated with the presence of dental caries among the study population (Teshome et al., 2021).

In North Africa, Osman et al. (2019) found a prevalence of about 16%, 31%, and 48% each for gingivitis, periodontitis, and dental caries (conditions that are associated with poor oral hygiene [Hakeem et al., 2019]) among a secondary school student population in Egypt. Meanwhile, another Egyptian study among kindergarten children aged 3 – 6 discovered a prevalence of about 61% and 7% for dental caries and gingivitis (Shalan & Bakr, 2018). In Algeria, according to the Global Burden of Disease study (2019), the prevalence of dental caries in primary teeth of children aged 1 – 9 is about 44%, while the prevalence of dental caries in permanent teeth of persons > 5 years and the burden of periodontal disease among adolescents is still appreciable.

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In Southern Africa, Samuelsson and Samuelsson (2018) reported a 32% and 82% prevalence of dental caries and periodontal disease among 117 teenagers aged 15 – 19 in Zimbabwe.

In West Africa, Seidu et al. (2021), in their GSHS Ghanaian study, reported a poor oral hygiene prevalence of about 37% among in-school adolescents aged 12 – 18.

In Nigeria, Oyedele et al. (2021) discovered a prevalence of about 13% and 22% for dental caries among a study population of suburban children aged 8 – 12 and their counterparts of the same age range in rural areas. The prevalence of poor oral hygiene was 18% for the suburban children group and 25% for their rural counterparts. Children with poor oral hygiene were noted to have an increased odds of developing dental caries. Osadolor and Iwuoha (2019) reported a prevalence of poor oral hygiene of 2% among a study population of primary public schoolchildren in South-eastern Nigeria.

2.1.1.3 POTENTIAL CONSEQUENCES OF POOR ORAL HYGIENE FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

Children are integral members of society, currently in a stage of life dedicated to assimilating societal norms and values; they embody potential stakeholders in the future development of society (Ogordi et al., 2022). Apart from the knowledge from family and social groups, children also get a lot of information from school that shapes their attitudes and behaviours (Nyatuka, 2020).

Poor oral hygiene has been significantly linked with the development of oral diseases (Dagnew et al., 2020; Dhage & Chougule, 2019; Goryawala, 2018; Hakeem et al., 2019; Popescu et al., 2021). The development of oral diseases interferes with a child's ability to eat, speak, laugh, learn, and play with peers; in other words, a child's quality of life (Bhuiyan et al., 2020). Furthermore, the development of oral diseases also worsens school attendance (yearly, more than fifty million

school hours are lost due to oral diseases) among schoolchildren, thereby hindering academic performance (Cabrera et al., 2022; Rebelo et al., 2019).

2.1.1.4 FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE ORAL HYGIENE HABITS AMONG SCHOOLCHILDREN

2.1.1.4.1 AGE

Oral diseases remain a major public health challenge in this 21st century worldwide (Bhuiyan et al., 2020) and continue to be influenced by the oral hygiene habits of its victims (AlGhamdi et al., 2020). School age is the developmental period of life when children learn the skills necessary to thrive in their surrounding environment (Ogordi et al., 2022). At around six, a child's motor skills are said to have been developed appreciably enough to produce suitable oral hygiene status via habitual tooth brushing (Chua et al., 2022). Likewise, with increasing age, there is an increase in the performance of life tasks, which has been proven to increase the effectiveness of toothbrushing among children (Batinić et al., 2020; Kerr et al., 2019); notwithstanding, some reports in scientific literature beg to differ (Singh et al., 2021). Sharma et al. (2019) and Bashirian et al. (2018) observed decreased oral hygiene habits among children with increasing age. On the other hand, Zambaldia et al. (2022) noticed an association between oral hygiene habits and age in schoolchildren aged 7 – 10. While a child's age is vital for the accrual of necessary oral hygiene habits, instituting positive oral hygiene routines as early as possible by parents and guardians is an essential prerequisite (Zambaldia et al., 2022).

2.1.1.4.2 GENDER

Gender, according to Vlassoff (2007), is a compilation of socially constructed roles, relationships, personality attributes, attitudes, behaviours, values, and the hierarchical allocation of power and influence that society attributes differentially to the two sexes (Kalu et al., 2020). As individuals progress from childhood to adolescence within the societal milieu, wherein they are

exposed to male and female figures such as parents, guardians, siblings, educators, peers, traders, religious authorities, and health workers, among others, the prominence of their gender roles intensifies (Kalu et al., 2020). This developmental trajectory, marked by multifaceted interactions with various members of society, significantly contributes to the moulding and delineation of their gender identity and the adoption of gender roles and characteristics (Kalu et al., 2020).

Gender has been reported to have an association with oral hygiene habits (Sadana et al., 2020), with some studies reporting the male gender to be associated with better oral hygiene habits (Monika & Nikitha, 2022; Parveen et al., 2018) compared to their female counterparts, while others, emphasising the converse as true (Ahmad et al., 2019; AlMalki et al., 2020; Onigbinde et al., 2020; Santoso et al., 2021).

2.1.1.4.3 HOUSEHOLD SIZE/COMPOSITION

According to the United Nations (2017), a household is a collective of individuals jointly providing sustenance, shelter, and other fundamental necessities (United Nations, 2019). Furthermore, the household size represents the count of individuals in a particular residence bound by blood, marriage, or adoption (United Nations, 2019). Simultaneously, the composition of a household refers to its delineation based on specific attributes of its members, including age, relationship to the household head, and the number of marital unions it encompasses (United Nations, 2019).

Household size and composition have been reported to be linked to oral hygiene habits in children (Trinh et al., 2021; Zambaldia et al., 2022), with children in larger household sizes having better oral hygiene habits that began earlier than their counterparts in smaller household sizes (Trinh et al., 2021). Similarly, children in a household composed of both parents had better oral hygiene habits than those with only one parent (Zambaldia et al., 2022).

2.1.1.4.4 FAMILY SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

Socioeconomic status (SES) measures an individual or family's economic and social standing (Chen et al., 2018). This multifaceted concept encompasses concrete, measurable elements, such as income or education, and subjective evaluations of one's position in the socioeconomic hierarchy (Navarro-Carrillo et al., 2020). Many literatures have identified three dimensions of family SES: family income, parents' educational attainment, and parents' occupational prestige (Chen et al., 2018).

SES has been reported to be linked to oral hygiene habits and, consequently, oral hygiene status among children (Mishra et al., 2019); Santoso et al. (2021) discovered poorer oral hygiene habits among Indonesian schoolchildren of lower SES. Similarly, Shitu et al. (2023) noticed better oral hygiene habits among Ethiopian Children whose fathers had a higher level of education, while Malhotra et al. (2021) revealed a deterioration in oral hygiene status, consequent upon oral hygiene habits with lower SES.

2.1.1.4.5 MEDIA

Media refers to a medium or device through which information is transferred from a sender to a receiver (Paul & Rai, 2021). Media presents in different forms, including traditional publishing (newspapers, periodicals, or books), traditional electronic media (broadcasting, broadband, cable, or satellite), motion pictures, video gaming, recorded music, advertising, and adaptations of the internet for any of these previously mentioned media (Paul & Rai, 2021).

In its diverse forms, media has been noted to be associated with children's oral hygiene habits (Nagarajappa et al., 2021), as it remains a major source/conduit for oral hygiene information. Hanif and Prasko (2018) emphasised the relevance of video media in improving oral hygiene knowledge and awareness [and consequently oral hygiene habits] among a group of elementary schoolchildren. Kabir et al. (2019) affirmed that media was an influential tool in shaping the oral

hygiene habits of children. Meanwhile, Pinge et al. (2023) recorded an improvement in schoolchildren's oral hygiene habits with media involvement in health education campaigns. Similarly, Sarwer-Foner et al. (2021) noticed an improvement in oral hygiene habits with the application of social media as a medium of oral health education.

2.1.1.4.6 SCHOOL TYPE/ENVIRONMENT

The type of school, whether public or private, a child attends is thought to be associated with the socioeconomic status (SES) of the child's family (Khalid et al., 2020). Private schools are suggested to cater for children of wealthier families compared to public schools, whose attendees are generally children from less affluent backgrounds (Khalid et al., 2020).

Oral hygiene habits have been reported in the literature to have a relationship with a child's school type or environment; Akaji et al. (2020), Jibo & Mubarak (2018) and Igbiosa et al. (2018) revealed that oral hygiene habits among 11 to 12-year-olds attending private schools were better than those attending public schools. Similarly, Gautam et al. (2022) and Namdev et al. (2021) discovered that children aged between 10 and 15 attending public schools had poorer oral hygiene [secondary to poor oral hygiene habits] than their counterparts in public schools.

2.1.1.4.7 PARENTAL ORAL HYGIENE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES

Knowledge refers to an individual's understanding, awareness, and familiarity with a particular subject, topic, or domain (Omorodion & Osadolor, 2021). It involves accumulating information through learning and experience, enabling an individual to comprehend and interpret facts, concepts, and principles (Omorodion & Osadolor, 2021).

Attitude refers to the predisposition or evaluation of one's feelings, beliefs, and behavioural tendencies toward a particular object, person, group, idea, or situation (Omorodion & Osadolor,

2021). It involves a combination of cognitive, affective, and behavioural components that shape an individual's response and inclination (Omorodion & Osadolor, 2021).

Practices, in general, denote the actions, behaviours, or activities that individuals engage in, often influenced by their knowledge and attitudes (Omorodion & Osadolor, 2021). In specific contexts, such as health, it may refer to habitual or intentional behaviours that impact individual or collective well-being (Omorodion & Osadolor, 2021).

Oral hygiene knowledge, attitudes, and practices have been reported to influence their children's oral hygiene habits (Pranno et al., 2022) and oral health status (Dikshit et al., 2018; Salama et al., 2020). Nepal and Mahomed (2020) discovered better toothbrushing habits among children aged 5 – 12, with parents with better knowledge and attitudes concerning oral hygiene than those with poorer knowledge and attitudes. Meanwhile, Munawar et al. (2022) noticed a strong positive correlation between the knowledge and attitudes of a group of parents with their children's oral hygiene [secondary to oral hygiene habits]. Noh (2020) and Rachmawati et al. (2018), in a similar vein, observed that parental knowledge, attitudes and practices concerning oral health were correlated with the oral hygiene habits of their children.

2.1.1.4.8 PEER GROUP

According to Spadafora et al. (2019), a peer group is a collective of individuals of roughly the same age sharing common interests, backgrounds, or social standings. Children learn and adopt oral hygiene habits more easily from their peers than adults (Joyani et al., 2018; Yeo et al., 2020). Less peer support is associated with poorer oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren (Santoso et al., 2021).

Roudsari et al. (2019) and Zikri et al. (2019) highlighted that the toothbrushing frequency of schoolchildren correlated with, and was greatly influenced by, the toothbrushing frequency of their peers.

2.1.1.4.9 ACCESS TO ORAL HYGIENE PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Access to oral hygiene products and services refers to an individual's freedom or ability to obtain or use oral hygiene products and services (Uguru et al., 2020). Oral hygiene products such as toothbrushes, toothpaste, dental floss, and mouthwash help to remove dental plaque and bacteria. Meanwhile, oral hygiene services, in the form of dental scaling and polishing (professional oral prophylaxis), help remove dental plaque, dental stains, calcified dental plaque, or dental calculus (Onyejaka et al., 2020). A significant barrier to a child accessing oral hygiene products and services, as outlined by Peres et al. (2019), is being born into a low-income family. A comparative study by Idowu et al. (2020) on the oral health disparity between *Almajiri* [street] children and their counterparts attending private senior secondary schools (PSSS) in Kano state, Nigeria, reported a 49% prevalence of poor oral hygiene amongst the *Almajiri* children, as compared to 3% amongst the PSSS children. In addition, 65% of the *Almajiri* children used a finger with water for cleaning their teeth compared to none (0%) of the PSSS children (Idowu et al., 2020).

2.1.1.4.10 BIRTH RANK

Birth rank, commonly called birth order, signifies the sequential arrangement of siblings' births within a family (Franz, 2018). Birth rank is believed to influence personality development and behaviour, with each position (the firstborn, middle child, youngest, *etcetera.*) thought to contribute to certain traits and characteristics (Franz, 2018).

Birth rank has also been linked to oral hygiene status and subsequent oral diseases in children (Singh & Vijayakumar, 2020), though some reports disagree (Mohammed & Mohamed, 2020;

Mahboobi et al., 2021). According to Oyedele et al. (2019), middleborns and firstborns exhibited poorer oral hygiene than lastborns. Conversely, Julihn et al. (2020) observed an elevated risk of caries incidence [secondary to poor oral hygiene habits] in laterborns, referencing firstborns as a baseline in their cohort study. In addition, Grieshaber et al. (2022) established that the risk of dental caries in laterborns more than tripled if the firstborn already had a caries disease. Depicted below is the literature map of the concepts reviewed so far [Figure 2].

Figure 2: A literature map of the concepts reviewed in the present study.

Source: Principal investigator (2024)

2.1.1.5 CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The conceptual model, centred on the conceptual review, proposes that a combination of individual, social, and environmental factors influence oral hygiene habits. Individual factors, such

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as age, gender, birth rank, oral health knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs, can directly influence oral hygiene habits. Social and environmental factors, such as family size and composition, family SES, parental level of education, parental knowledge, attitudes and practices towards oral health, access to traditional and digital media, access to dental care, peer group, and school type, can also influence oral hygiene habits directly or indirectly through their influence on individual factors.

Figure 3: Conceptual Model

Source: Principal investigator (2024)

The figure above shows the relationship between a range of factors or independent variables (individual, social, and environmental) and how they all interact to influence the oral hygiene habits of schoolchildren (dependent variable).

2.2 EMPIRICAL STUDIES

2.2.1 KNOWLEDGE OF ORAL HYGIENE HABITS AMONG SCHOOLCHILDREN

In a study by Akinyamoju et al. (2020) titled ‘Oral health knowledge and practice: influence of sociodemographic factors in rural Nigerian School children’, involving 778 schoolchildren aged 7 – 17, it was observed that 87.2% of the respondents exhibited poor oral hygiene knowledge.

Turning to Nzomiwu et al.’s (2022) study titled ‘Oral Health Knowledge and Behaviour among Public Primary Schoolchildren in Lagos, Nigeria’, nearly half (47.7%) of the pupils exhibited insufficient oral health knowledge. Additionally, most respondents had never visited a dentist (75.0%), and dental floss use was reported by only 33.4%.

Examining the study by Elzahaf et al. (2019) titled ‘Oral health practices, knowledge, and attitudes among primary schoolchildren in Derna City, Libya’, findings indicated that over two-thirds (67.2%) of the respondents possessed poor knowledge about oral health [hygiene].

In their 2021 study, ‘Oral health knowledge and practices among elementary pupils attending Saint Louis College, City of San Fernando, La Union, The Philippines’, Fadare et al. found that a minority demonstrated unsatisfactory knowledge regarding the causes (12.8%) and preventive measures (13.8%) of oral diseases among 293 pupils in grades 4 to 6.

Moving to Abate et al.’s (2020) study, ‘Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices Toward Oral Hygiene Among Students of Medhanealem High School, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia’, among 320 secondary school students, 62.8% demonstrated inadequate knowledge regarding oral hygiene. Notably, the chewing stick (*Mefakiya*) emerged as the most prevalent oral hygiene aid, utilized by 51.0% of the students for teeth cleaning.

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In the study conducted by Nagarajappa et al. (2021), ‘Sources of Oral Health Information and its Relationship on Knowledge Among Indian Adolescents’, involving 1330 adolescents aged 13 – 15, oral hygiene knowledge was unsatisfactory. Approximately 45% were aware of fluoride; out of this group, only 36% correctly identified fluoride’s action as preventing cavities.

Moving on to Alshloul’s (2023) study titled ‘Oral Health Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Among School Children in Abha-Saudi Arabia’, encompassing 800 respondents, approximately 41% exhibited unsatisfactory oral health knowledge.

In their 2018 study titled ‘Oral hygiene knowledge habits and practices among primary school pupils in Kano Nigeria’, Jibo and Mubarak compared oral hygiene habits among primary school children in Gwale local government, Kano state. The findings revealed a higher level of oral hygiene knowledge among students in private schools (63.5%) than among public school students (36.5%).

In Bhuiyan et al.’s (2020) study, ‘Oral Hygiene Awareness and Practices among a Sample of Primary School Children in Rural Bangladesh’, among 150 schoolchildren aged 5 – 12, the findings revealed a notable lack of knowledge about oral hygiene habits. Notably, 81% of the children utilized toothpaste and toothbrush for cleaning their teeth, while 15% employed a finger or chewing stick (Neem) with abrasives like toothpaste, charcoal, ash, and salt. Moreover, 83% of schoolchildren brushed once daily, with the remaining 17% practising twice-daily brushing.

Finally, in Sharmila et al.’s (2020) study titled ‘Knowledge, attitude and practice on oral hygiene among primary school children in an urban area of Kancheepuram District, Tamil Nadu,’ involving 250 primary schoolchildren aged 8 – 10, about 34% of respondents demonstrated poor knowledge of oral hygiene.

In summary, the amalgamation of these studies emphasizes a notable gap in oral health knowledge across different demographics. The findings consistently underscore insufficient awareness regarding oral hygiene practices and the causes of oral diseases among schoolchildren.

2.2.2 DENTAL SERVICE UTILISATION BY SCHOOLCHILDREN

Dental service utilization, as defined by Brown et al. (1999), refers to the percentage of the population accessing dental services within a specified time (Ghanbari-Jahromi et al., 2023).

In the investigation titled ‘Preventive Oral Health Care Use and Oral Health Status among US Children: 2016 National Survey of Children’s Health’, conducted by Lebrun-Harris et al. (2019) among 46,100 children aged 2 – 17, it was disclosed that 82% of the overall respondents had sought preventive dental care within the preceding 12 months.

In a similar enquiry titled ‘Oral Health Problems and Utilization of Dental Services among Spanish and Immigrant Children and Adolescents’, by Portero de la Cruz and Cebrino (2020), encompassing 4568 Spanish and immigrant children and adolescents aged 3 – 14, it was found that 64.6% of Spanish children had visited the dentist within the last 12 months, in contrast to 48.2% of immigrant children.

Moreover, a cross-sectional study titled ‘Predictors of low dental service utilization among school children in Mekelle, Northern Ethiopia,’ conducted by Mohammed et al. (2023) and involving 398 schoolchildren aged 6 – 15, ascertained an overall dental service utilization rate of 10.6% within the past 12 months. Significantly, a considerable majority of respondents (89.4%) asserted never having seen a dentist.

Similarly, a study titled ‘Utilization of dental care service and associated factors among pre-school children in northwest China over the past decade’, by Hu et al. (2023) among 399 five-year-old-

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caregiver pairs in the year 2005 and 492 five-year-old-caregiver pairs in the year 2015, reported that the utilization of dental care services in 2005 and 2015 stood at 20.8% and 20.0%, respectively.

In the same vein, the study titled ‘Maternal knowledge, dental service utilization, and self-reported oral hygiene practices in relation to the oral health of preschool children in Lagos, Nigeria’ by Olatosi et al. (2020) among 334 mothers observed a dental service utilization rate of 21.9%. Notably, 78.1% of the respondents attested to never having visited a dentist.

Maffioletti et al. (2020), in their study titled ‘Predisposing, enabling, and need characteristics of dental services utilization among socially deprived schoolchildren’, delineated that out of a total of 358 twelve-year-old schoolchildren, only 47.8% availed dental services within 12 months.

Additionally, the epidemiological survey titled ‘Socioeconomic Inequalities in the Use of Dental Care Services during Early Childhood’ by Souza et al. (2018) among 7241 five-year-old children reported a 53.2% lifetime utilization of dental services.

In another survey titled ‘Andersen health care utilization model: A survey on factors affecting the utilization of dental health services among school children’, by Nagdev et al. (2023), among 1100 schoolchildren aged 13 – 15, a dental service utilization of 21.9% was discovered.

In the study by Al Agili and Farsi (2020) titled ‘Need for Dental Care Drives Utilization of Dental Services Among Children in Saudi Arabia’, among 1688 third and eighth graders, it was disclosed that 25.5% of respondents had never utilized dental care services. Moreover, among the 1688 participants, 31.8% visited the dentist within the last six months, 14.7% within the last 6 – 12 months, 14.3% within the last 1 – 3 years, and 7.2% last visited more than three years ago.

Finally, the study by Sharma et al. (2019) titled ‘Oral Hygiene Practices and Factors Affecting Oral Health Service Utilization among Children (11–14 Years) of Government School of Nikol

Ward of East Zone of Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India’, involving 200 students, recorded a dental service utilization rate of 32.5%. Notably, an average of 67.5% of respondents had never visited a dentist before.

In summary, the collection of these varieties of studies offers a comprehensive view of dental service utilization among schoolchildren globally. Noteworthy patterns include a substantial emphasis on preventive care, disparities influenced by socioeconomic factors, and a considerable percentage of respondents reporting never having visited a dentist.

2.2.3 ORAL HYGIENE STATUS AND SCHOOLCHILDREN

In a study by Ulloa et al. (2020) titled ‘Oral hygiene in schools of 6 years of age of the Baños Rural Parish - Ecuador’ among 198 six-year-old schoolchildren, it was discovered that the oral hygiene status of most respondents was good, and there was no significant difference between the two genders.

A similar study by Sony et al. (2021) titled ‘Knowledge and Practice of Oral Health and Hygiene and Oral Health Status among School Going Adolescents in a Rural Area of Sylhet District, Bangladesh’ among 90 respondents revealed that 31% of the participants exhibited good oral hygiene, 59% had fair oral hygiene status, while 10% had poor oral hygiene.

Doley and Srivastava (2021), in the study titled ‘Oral hygiene status and its association with oral hygiene practices among school-going children of rural and urban areas in Kamrup district, Assam, among 1,501 schoolchildren aged 13 – 14’, observed that oral hygiene status was significantly poorer among rural compared to urban respondents, among males than females, and among those who use finger compared to a toothbrush for teeth cleaning.

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Meanwhile, Lucero et al. (2019), in the study titled ‘Oral hygiene index in 12-year-old schoolchildren of the Checa parish in Canton Cuenca, Province of Azuay, Ecuador, 2016’ among 109 schoolchildren aged 12, noticed that the oral hygiene status of most respondents was good.

Furthermore, Akinyamoju et al. (2020), in their study titled ‘Oral health knowledge and practice: influence of sociodemographic factors in rural Nigerian Schoolchildren’, involving 778 schoolchildren aged 7 – 17, observed that the oral hygiene status of most respondents was poor, and that gingivitis was common amongst the respondents.

Moreover, Osadolor and Iwuoha (2019), in their study titled ‘Oral hygiene status of primary school children’ among 123 primary schoolchildren aged 8 – 14, recognised that the oral hygiene status of most respondents was fair.

In the investigation titled ‘Social predictors of oral hygiene status in school children from suburban Nigeria’ by Oyedele et al. (2019), among a sample of 2,107 schoolchildren aged 8–16, the oral hygiene status was reported as good in 44.7% of respondents, fair in 38.2% of respondents, and poor in 17.1% of respondents.

In a separate enquiry titled ‘Oral Health Status Among 12-Year-Old Schoolchildren in Kosovo’ by Ferizi et al. (2020) among a sample of 1,204 schoolchildren aged 12 from both urban and rural areas, indicated that the oral hygiene status of most of the examined schoolchildren was poor.

The cross-sectional study on the relationship between oral hygiene and socioeconomic status among 15-year-old schoolchildren conducted by Maholtra et al. (2021) among 1,038 respondents reported that oral hygiene status was good in 46.3% of respondents, fair in 38.2% of respondents, and poor in 15.4% of respondents. Notably, poorer oral hygiene status was significantly associated with a lower brushing frequency and SES.

Another enquiry titled ‘Oral health awareness and oral hygiene status of 12- and 15-year-old children in Chennai’ by Ganesh et al. (2019) among 1,600 respondents outlined that the majority of participants (63.6%) exhibited fair oral hygiene status.

In summary, a compilation of multiple studies on oral hygiene status among schoolchildren from various regions reveals notable trends. Overall, several studies indicate a substantial proportion of participants exhibiting fair oral hygiene status. Variations exist, however, with some studies reporting good oral hygiene; in contrast, others highlight a prevalence of poor oral health, often associated with factors like rural residence, gender, socioeconomic status, and oral health knowledge.

2.3.4 PREDICTORS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABITS AMONG SCHOOLCHILDREN

According to the Britannica Dictionary (2023), a predictor is defined as ‘something that shows whether or not something is likely to happen’; in the present context, this can be interpreted as a variable or factor that provides information about a particular outcome happening or not.

In a study conducted by Batinić et al. (2020), which aimed to establish a correlation between children’s oral hygiene index and dietary habits among 102 respondents aged 0 – 18, age emerged as a predictor of dietary habits. Dietary habits, in particular, were observed to deteriorate with increasing age.

Aguilar-Polo and Mateo-Solis (2021) conducted another study analysing the oral health knowledge and oral hygiene habits of 234 Peruvian students. The findings indicated that a strong influence exists between good oral hygiene knowledge and good oral hygiene habits.

Similarly, Deng et al. (2019) investigated tooth brushing behaviour and influencing factors among middle school students in Chongqing, China, involving 3,902 students aged 12 – 15. Results

revealed that the father's and mother's education level and awareness of the necessity of regular oral examination were significant predictors of good toothbrushing habits.

In a study by Oyedele et al. (2019) titled 'Social predictors of oral hygiene status in school children from suburban Nigeria', which involved a sample of 2,107 schoolchildren aged 8–16, age, gender, socioeconomic status, and birth rank were identified as significant social predictors of oral hygiene status. The odds of having good oral hygiene were reduced for children 13 – 16 years old, male, and belonging to a low SES. The odds of having good oral hygiene increased for children who were last-born compared with those who were first-born.

Santoso et al. (2021) explored lifestyle and psychosocial correlates of oral hygiene practices among 11,142 Indonesian adolescents aged 11 – 18. The study revealed that male gender, lower socioeconomic status, poor dietary habits, longer sedentary time, drug use, psychological distress, lack of peer support, and absence of parental support were predictors of infrequent tooth brushing.

Zambaldia et al. (2022) investigated the influence of children's maternal and socioeconomic characteristics on oral hygiene habits among 1,282 students aged 7 – 10. Living with both parents, having a past dental appointment, a history of cavity experience, and owning a toothbrush emerged as predictors for more favourable oral hygiene habits.

In a similar study by Kabir et al. (2019) focusing on knowledge and oral hygiene practice among 474 students in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh, age was a significant predictor of oral hygiene practice. The frequency and duration of toothbrushing increased significantly with age.

Gebregiorgis et al. (2021) examined the level of oral hygiene practices and its association with socio-demographic characteristics among middle school students in low-income countries. The

study identified the female gender as a predictor of better oral hygiene practices among the respondents.

Shitu et al. (2023) conducted a cross-sectional study among 423 preparatory school students in Gondar City, Northwest Ethiopia, aiming to evaluate oral hygiene behaviour and its determinants. Results indicated that a respondent's father's educational status, being from a private school, good knowledge about oral hygiene, and positive attitudes toward oral hygiene were significant predictors of better oral hygiene habits.

Finally, Badarch et al. (2021) aimed to determine the prevalence and correlates of poor oral hygiene in Mongolian school-going students. The study identified several significant predictors of poor oral hygiene [habits], including male gender, inadequate fruit and vegetable intake, parents' smoking, exposure to second-hand smoke, poor parental supervision and connectedness, physical inactivity, and sedentary behaviour.

In summary, varied predictors impact oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren. Age consistently influences dietary and toothbrushing habits, while good oral hygiene knowledge correlates with positive practices. Socioeconomic factors like parents' education and family structure play a role, with gender affecting oral hygiene practices. Lifestyle factors such as dietary habits, sedentary behaviour, and exposure to second-hand smoke have also been linked to oral hygiene.

2.3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The social cognitive theory (SCT) is a theoretical framework widely used in health promotion, given its emphasis on the individual and the environment. The theory was developed by Albert Bandura (1986); it postulates that learning takes place within a social setting

characterized by dynamic and reciprocal interactions between the individual, the environment, and the behaviour (Devi et al., 2022). The model considers how an individual acquires and sustains a behaviour (Devi et al., 2022). The SCT consists of the following six key constructs or concepts (Devi et al., 2022):

1. **Reciprocal Determinism:** At the core of SCT, this concept underscores the dynamic and reciprocal interaction involving, for example, a schoolchild (the individual), the external social context (environment), and specific behaviours like toothbrushing and the use of dental floss.

2. **Behavioural Capability:** This aspect delves into an individual schoolchild's tangible ability to execute behaviours, relying on essential knowledge and skills. To successfully perform a behaviour, the schoolchild must grasp what needs to be done and how to do it, with learning influenced by the consequences of their actions and impacting their immediate environment.

3. **Observational Learning:** Emphasizing the role of modelling behaviours, this concept asserts that schoolchildren can observe and replicate actions like toothbrushing and the use of dental floss demonstrated by significant others such as parents, siblings, peers, teachers, or other influential figures.

4. **Reinforcements:** Focused on internal or external responses to a schoolchild's behaviours, such as the use of a straw while taking a soft drink or the use of dental floss, reinforcements can be positive [compliments from parents and teachers] or negative [sneers from siblings and peers]. The above construct closely ties to the reciprocal relationship between a schoolchild's behaviour and environment.

5. **Expectations:** This concept explores the expected outcomes of a schoolchild's behaviour. These outcomes can be health-related [avoiding tartar and gum disease] or non-health-related [receiving

praise from parents, classmates, or teachers for maintaining clean teeth]. Anticipated consequences influence the successful completion of behaviour and derive from past experiences.

6. **Self-efficacy:** This element reflects a schoolchild's confidence in successfully performing a behaviour like twice daily toothbrushing. Self-efficacy is shaped by the schoolchild's specific capabilities, individual factors, and environmental influences, including barriers and facilitators.

2.3.1 APPLICATION OF THE SCT TO THE PRESENT STUDY

IDENTIFYING KEY PREDICTORS

1. **Reciprocal Determinism:** The study will explore how various environmental factors [school type and media] interact with individual factors [age, gender, and birth rank] to predict oral hygiene habits.
2. **Behavioural Capability:** The study will assess the levels of oral hygiene habits of schoolchildren and how access to dental care resources plays a role.
3. **Observational Learning:** The study will investigate the influence of role models [parents, siblings, and peers] on children's adoption of different oral hygiene habits.
4. **Reinforcements:** The study will identify positive and negative reinforcements [rewards, punishments] that children receive for good oral hygiene habits and how these affect their behaviour.
5. **Expectations:** The study will explore the health-related and non-health-related consequences children anticipate from good oral hygiene and how these expectations influence their behaviour.

6. **Self-efficacy:** The study will assess the schoolchildren's confidence in their ability to properly brush their teeth, floss, and maintain good oral hygiene and how this self-efficacy influences their actual behaviour.

DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE INTERVENTIONS

Based on the identified predictors, the study will inform the design of interventions that target specific factors influencing oral hygiene habits. These interventions will focus on the following:

1. **Improving knowledge and skills:** Providing educational programs and practical demonstrations of proper oral hygiene techniques.
2. **Promoting positive role models:** Training parents, teachers, and peers to model good oral hygiene behaviours.
3. **Designing effective reinforcement systems:** Implementing reward systems for consistent good oral hygiene practice and addressing social pressures that discourage it.
4. **Managing expectations:** Emphasizing good oral hygiene's positive health and social consequences.
5. **Boosting self-efficacy:** Helping children develop confidence in their ability to maintain good oral hygiene through strategies such as goal setting, self-monitoring, and positive reinforcement.

2.4 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER

The literature review employed varying methodologies, combining electronic database searches and manual exploration, specifically emphasising oral hygiene habits in schoolchildren.

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

Approximately ninety recent and reliable articles underwent scrutiny, deliberately excluding those centred on adult and infant populations. The chapter highlighted the significance of oral hygiene, particularly during the schooling period, and systematically categorized the literature into conceptual literature, theoretical framework, and empirical studies.

In the conceptual literature, practices for maintaining oral hygiene, such as toothbrushing and regular dentist visits, were intricately detailed. The review underscored the prevalence of poor oral hygiene in lower-income schoolchildren, notably in Caribbean countries. It explored the potential consequences, including the development of oral diseases, reduced quality of life, and loss of school time. Additionally, it examined various factors influencing oral hygiene habits in children, such as age, gender, household size, family socioeconomic status, school type, tradition, digital media access, peer group influence, access to oral hygiene products, birth rank, and parental oral hygiene knowledge, attitude, and practices.

The conceptual model proposed that oral hygiene habits result from an interplay of individual and social/environmental factors. Individual aspects like age, gender, birth rank, and oral health knowledge directly influence oral hygiene habits. On the other hand, social and environmental factors, including family size, socioeconomic status, parental education, attitudes, practices, media access, dental care availability, peer influence, and school type, can impact these habits directly or indirectly by influencing individual factors.

The chapter's theoretical framework utilized the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) by Albert Bandura, exploring the acquisition and maintenance of behaviours like toothbrushing and dental floss use among schoolchildren. The six critical constructs within SCT were discussed, encompassing reciprocal determinism, behavioural capability, observational learning, reinforcements, expectations, and self-efficacy.

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

The review of empirical studies on oral hygiene among schoolchildren highlighted a significant knowledge gap, revealing insufficient awareness of oral hygiene practices and causes of oral diseases. The amalgamation of these studies provided a global perspective on dental service utilization, emphasizing patterns like a focus on preventive care, socioeconomic disparities, and a substantial percentage reporting never visiting a dentist. The review noted variations in oral hygiene status, with some studies indicating fair to good oral health and others revealing a prevalence of poor oral health associated with factors like rural residence, gender, socioeconomic status, and oral health knowledge. The review emphasized several predictors impacting oral hygiene habits, including age, socioeconomic factors, gender, and lifestyle choices.

In summary, the literature review provided a comprehensive overview of oral health and hygiene literature, emphasizing its crucial role in the overall well-being of schoolchildren, considering various socio-economic factors.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter highlights the various materials and methods that were used in this research under the following subheadings:

1. Study Design
2. Study Location
3. Target Population
4. Sample Size Calculation
5. Study Population
6. Sample/Sampling Technique
 1. Inclusion Criteria
 2. Exclusion Criteria
7. Study Instruments
 1. Validity
 2. Reliability
8. Statistical Analysis
9. Method of data collection
10. Ethical Approval

3.1 STUDY DESIGN

This study employed a cross-sectional observational study design to examine the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City. The sampling of study participants was conducted utilising a multi-staged sampling technique.

3.2 STUDY LOCATION

The study was conducted at sixteen randomly selected primary schools, both public and private, in Benin City, Edo State, specifically in the Oredo and Egor local government areas (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023a). The state is an inland state in central southern Nigeria, bordered by Kogi, Anambra, Delta, Ondo, and the Niger River.

Benin City, situated at 6°26'N and 5°41'E (Ben-Amos, 2018), serves as the capital of Edo State and is renowned for its historical significance involving 'bronze' or rather brass work dating back to the 13th century. Home to the University of Benin, Benson Idahosa University, and various educational institutions, the city plays a vital role in Nigeria's rubber production, with processing plants, a crepe factory, and the Rubber Research Institute nearby (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023b).

3.3 TARGET POPULATION

The target population for this study was all primary schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION

Since the outcome variable for this study was a proportion and hence a categorical outcome, the sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula for calculating single samples (Rahman, 2023).

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha})^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where n = minimum sample size or the desired sample size when the population is infinite.

Z_{α} = Standard normal variate of the type I error (for a type I error of 0.05, Z is 1.96 (at 95% confidence value))

p = Expected proportion of the factor under study = 50%

d = Absolute error of precision 5% or 0.05 was chosen for the present study.

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha})^2 p(1-p)}{d^2} = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 384.16 = 384 \text{ (Approximately)}$$

$$n = 384$$

Because the population of this study was finite, the formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

(finite population correction factor) should have been used to calculate the adjusted sample size.

However, since the minimum sample size required (384) was less than 10% of the study population size (12,122), the adjusted sample size was not calculated.

Furthermore, 10% of the calculated minimum required sample size n was added to the minimum required sample size to accommodate for possible non-response from the prospective participants ($384 + 38.4 = 422.4$ or 424 [rounded up to the next closest even number]). Thus, a sample size of

four hundred and twenty-four (424), which is greater than the minimum sample size required (384), was used for this study.

3.5 STUDY POPULATION

The study subjects comprised public and private primary schoolchildren in Benin City (Egor and Oredo), to be precise, pupils in their final year of primary education. According to data from the Edo State Ministry of Education (2016), the calculated population of final year (class 5 or 6) pupils was 6450 in Egor and 5672 pupils in Oredo Local Government Area. Thus, the study population was 12,122 (i.e., 6450 + 5672). This research study was undertaken among final-year pupils in public and private primary schools in Benin City [Egor and Oredo local government areas], Edo state.

$$\text{Sampling fraction} = \frac{\text{Sample size } (n)}{\text{Sample frame } (N)} = \frac{424}{12,122} = 0.035$$

Number of respondents = sampling fraction × number of pupils in each local government area [Table 1].

Table 1: Proportional allocation of pupils to each of the two local government areas.

Local government area	The population of pupils in the final year	Sampling fraction	Number of respondents for primary school final year
Egor	6450	0.035	226
Oredo	5672	0.035	198
Total	12122		424

3.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A multi-stage sampling technique was used for this study.

Stage 1: Selection of Local Government Areas (LGAs)

The LGAs were assigned numbers as follows:

1. Ikpoba-Okha
2. Egor
3. Ovia North-East
4. Oredo

Two LGAs (Egor [2] and Oredo [4]) were randomly selected from a total number of four using a simple random number generator.

Stage 2: Allotment of sampling units to each of the two selected LGA

Out of the total sample size of four hundred and twenty-four (424), 226 sampling units were allocated to Egor LGA, while 198 were allocated to Oredo [Table 1].

Stage 3: Selection of Schools from local governments

With the help of a sampling frame [a list of schools (Federal Ministry of Education, 2023)], two public schools were randomly selected from each of the sampled local government areas, making a total of four public schools. Meanwhile, three private primary schools were randomly selected from Oredo local government area and nine from Egor, making a total of 12 private schools [Table 2].

Table 2: Proportional allocation of public and private schools from the two local government areas

Local government areas	Number of private schools	Number of public schools	The ratio of sampled private to public schools
Oredo	131	86	3:2
Egor	169	38	9:2
Total	300	124	12:4

Stage 4: Selection of School class and participants.

From each of the selected schools, one or more final-year classes were selected judgmentally by virtue of their maturity compared to their lower-class counterparts. In Egor, 185 sampling units were shared unequally (20 sampling units to each school, with five sampling units as the remainder) among the nine selected private schools; the remaining sampling units were allocated to the school with the largest number of schoolchildren in a selected class, as evidenced by the class register. Meanwhile, 41 sampling units were shared unequally (20 sampling units to each school, with one sampling unit as the remainder) between the two selected public schools; the remaining sampling units were allocated to the school with the largest number of schoolchildren in a selected class, as evidenced by the class register.

In Oredo, 119 sampling units were shared unequally (39 sampling units to each school, with two sampling units as the remainder) among the three selected private schools; the remaining sampling units were allocated to the school with the largest number of schoolchildren in a selected class, as evidenced by the class register.

Likewise, 79 sampling units were shared unequally (39 sampling units to each school, with one sampling unit as the remainder) between the two selected public schools; the remaining sampling

units were allocated to the school with the largest number of schoolchildren in a selected class, as evidenced by the class register.

For each of the randomly selected classes, all participants present in that class on the day of the study were eligible for selection into the study. Using the class register as a sample frame, each pupil on the class register was assigned a number that begins with one for the first person on the register and down to the last person on the register. Using a simple random number generator, participants were selected for the study if their assigned numbers matched the random number generator's output. This procedure was continued until the required sample for a particular school was met. If the allotted sample size to the school was not achieved due to a reduced number of pupils in a class, after sampling everyone in a particular class, the sampling units in another final-year class of the same school were randomly sampled until the desired sample size was achieved. If this contingency measure was not achievable due to a reduced number of pupils in this class and other final year classes [if any] also in this school, another school of the same school type in the same local government area was sampled, and the procedure as mentioned above repeated until the sample size was achieved.

3.5.1 INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Participants attending public and private primary schools in Benin City.
2. Participants in the final year (class 5 or 6) of primary education in Benin City.
3. Participants who were present at school on the day of the study.
4. Participants that are willing to give assent to participate in the study.
5. Participants whose parents/guardians give consent to participate in the study.

3.5.2 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Schoolchildren who did not give assent to participate in the study
2. Schoolchildren not attending public and private secondary schools in Benin City.
3. Schoolchildren not in their final year of primary school in Benin City.
4. Schoolchildren who are absent from school on the day of the study.
5. Participants whose parents/guardians do not consent to participate in the study.
6. Schoolchildren with significant cognitive impairments.
7. Schoolchildren who cannot understand English language or Pidgin English.

3.7 STUDY INSTRUMENTS

The instrument for assessing the predictors of oral hygiene habits among the respondents was a questionnaire (Appendix II) that was interviewer-administered while the respondent was seated comfortably on an armchair. The questionnaire comprised two sections: the first section aimed to gather sociodemographic information from the participants. Meanwhile, the second section comprised nineteen (19) items; it delved into the participants' oral hygiene habits and explored factors influencing them.

3.7.1 VALIDITY

The questionnaire underwent a thorough validation process involving an expert review by a paediatric dentist and the project supervisor for face and content validity. A pilot test was also undertaken among a small group of schoolchildren to assess clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility.

3.7.2 RELIABILITY

The internal consistency of the questionnaire was assessed using 5% of the sample size for pre-testing. The questionnaire was administered to 20 pupils from a primary school not involved in the study by about 10 am while seated comfortably on an armchair. One week later, a re-administration of the questionnaire was conducted for the 20 pupils. The recorded scores from the first and second tests were entered, processed, and analysed using the IBM SPSS version 25 software. A Cohen kappa value of 0.735 (good agreement) was discovered on analysis (Appendix III)

3.7.3 INSTRUMENT ITEM SCORING AND INDEX CATEGORISATION

To create a composite oral hygiene habit index among the respondents, scores were assigned for the following items on the questionnaire: items 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 13, 15, and 17, respectively. Each item was worth a score of 1 for a correct response and a score of 0 for an incorrect response, making the lowest score attainable 0 and the highest score attainable 9. In situations where an item consisted of more than one sub-item, the score of 1 was divided equally among the sub-items. The oral hygiene habits of respondents were then categorized as follows:

1. 0 – 4.49: poor
2. 4.50 – 6.79: fair
3. 6.80 – 9.00: good.

3.8 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Collected data was entered, cleaned, and analysed using IBM SPSS statistics for Windows, version 25 (Armonk, NY: IBM Corporation 2021). The normality of the data was tested using a histogram, stem and leaf plot, QQ plot and detrended QQ plot, box and whisker plot, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and the Shapiro-Wilk's test. Descriptive statistics were expressed as

proportions, mean (SD), and median (IQR); tables were employed to enhance clarity. Inferential statistics of association were conducted using the non-parametric tests [Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test] for variables that were distribution-free. Also, a multinomial logistic regression was computed to determine the factors predicting good and fair oral hygiene habits among participants.

3.9 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The study involved a two-week data collection period, utilizing a well-timed administration of questionnaires in the morning when pupils were alert and less stressed. The principal investigator and four assistants, including the class teacher, administered the questionnaire. Rigorous investigator-led training of the research assistants was conducted to emphasise unbiased data collection and a standardized questionnaire administration. The principal investigator guiding the process ensured consistency and reliability in the gathered information.

3.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

A letter of introduction for ethical clearance was collected from the Head of the Department of Public Health Science, National Open University of Nigeria, through the university's ethical committee. Ethical approval was sought and obtained [**Approval number: HA/737/24/C/02060211**] from the Research and Ethics Committee, Edo State Ministry of Health (Appendix V). Furthermore, informed consent was obtained from the parents of the participants following the Belmont report relevant to research ethics involving human subjects, including principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice (Appendix I). Meanwhile, the assent of the participants was sought and obtained on the day of the study.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the results of the study. In this study, all 424 interviewer-administered questionnaires were completed, giving a response rate of 100%.

4.2 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA ACCORDING TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

4.2.1 SECTION A: SOCIAL-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 3: Social-demographic characteristics of the respondents (n = 424)

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age (years)		
9	28	6.6
10	114	26.9
11	90	21.2
12	102	24.1
13	46	10.8
14	18	4.2
15	14	3.3
16	4	0.9
17	8	1.9
Mean (SD) = 11.48 (1.68); Median (IQR) = 11.0 (12.0, 10.0) years		
Gender		
Male	194	45.8
Female	230	54.2
Total	424	100

Table 3.1: Social-demographic characteristics of the respondents (n = 424).

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Father's Level of Education		
Primary	80	18.9
Secondary	146	34.4
Tertiary	198	46.7
Mother's Level of Education		
Primary	82	19.3
Secondary	176	41.5
Tertiary	166	39.2
Birth Rank		
Firstborn	130	30.7
Second born	72	17.0
Middle born	136	32.1
Last born	80	18.9
Only child	6	1.4
Number of Children per Household		
1 – 2	42	9.9
3 – 4	212	50.0
5 – 6	124	29.2
7 – 8	40	9.4
9 – 12	6	1.4
Mean (SD) = 4.39 (1.67); Median (IQR) = 4.0 (5.0, 3.0)		
Total	424	100

Table 3.2: Social-demographic characteristics of the respondents (n = 424).

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Family Size		
2 – 3	10	2.4
4 – 5	116	27.4
6 – 7	192	45.3
8 – 9	80	18.9
10 – 14	26	6.1
Mean (SD) = 6.52 (1.84); Median (IQR) = 6.0 (7.8, 5.0)		
Family Composition		
Father and Mother	338	79.7
Mother (only)	44	10.4
Father (only)	18	4.2
Guardian	24	5.7
School Type		
Public	234	55.2
Private	190	44.8
School Location		
Egor	226	53.3
Oredo	198	46.7
Total	424	100

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Tables 3, 3.1 and 3.2 explain that in terms of the ages of the respondents, 28 (6.6%) of respondents were nine years old, 114 (26.9%) were ten years old, 90 (21.2%) were 11 years old, 102 (24.1%) were 12 years old, 46 (10.8%) were 13 years old, 18(4.2%) were 14 years old, 14 (3.3%) were 15 years old, while 12 (2.8%) of respondent were between 16 and 17 years old. The median age was 11.0 (IQR: 12.0, 10.0) years.

Moving on from age to the gender of the respondents, 194 (45.8%) of respondents were male, whereas 230 (54.2%) of respondents were females.

In addition to gender, it was discovered that the highest educational level attained by the respondents' fathers was primary in 80 (18.9%) of respondents, secondary in 146 (34.4%) of respondents, and tertiary in 198 (46.7%) of respondents.

Likewise, it was ascertained that the highest educational level attained by the respondents' mothers was primary in 82 (19.3%) of respondents, secondary in 176 (41.5%) of respondents, and tertiary in 166 (39.2%) of respondents.

Shifting the viewpoint from the highest educational level attained by the respondents' mothers to birth rank, it was observed that 130 (30.7%) of respondents were firstborns, 72 (17.0%) were secondborns, 132 (32.1%) were middleborns, 80 (18.9%) were lastborns; meanwhile, 6 (1.4%) of respondents were only children.

Besides birth rank, the number of children per household of respondents was between 1 and 2 in 42 (9.9%) of respondents; between 3 and 4 in 212 (50.0%) of respondents; between 5 and 6 in 124 (29.2%) of respondents; between 7 and 8 in 40 (9.4%) of respondents, and between 9 and 12 in 6 (1.4%) of respondents. The median number of children per household of respondents was 4.0 (IQR: 5.0, 3.0)

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Similarly, the family size of the respondents was shown to be between 2 and 3 in 10 (2.4%) of respondents, between 4 and 5 in 116 (27.4%) of respondents, between 6 and 7 in 192 (45.3%) of respondents; between 8 and 9 in 80 (18.9%) of respondents, and between 10 and 14 in 26 (6.1%) of respondents. The median size for a family per respondent was 6 (IQR: 7.8, 5.0).

As far as the family composition of the respondents was concerned, the family composition included a father and a mother in 338 (79.7%) of respondents; a mother only in 44 (10.4%) of respondents; a father only in 18 (4.2%) of respondents and a guardian in 24 (5.7%) of respondents.

Furthermore, regarding the school type of the respondents, 234 (55.2%) of respondents attended a public school; meanwhile, 190 (44.8%) of respondents attended a private school.

In the same vein, as regards the local government area where the schools of the studied respondents were located, it was uncovered that the school location was in Egor in 226 (53.3%) of respondents. Meanwhile, the school location was in Oredo in 198 (46.7%) of respondents.

4.2.2 SECTION B: THE LEVELS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABIT.

Table 4.0: The oral hygiene habits of the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Do you brush your teeth daily?		
Yes	422	99.5
No	2	0.5
With respect to item 1 above, how many times do you brush in a day whenever you brush?		
Once	246	58.0
Twice	172	40.6
Three times	6	1.4
When, in relation to meals, do you do it?		
Before meal/s	350	82.5
After meal/s	12	2.8
Before breakfast and after dinner	62	14.6
For how long, in minutes, do you brush your teeth?		
Less than 3 minutes	216	50.9
3 minutes or greater	208	49.1
What do you use to brush your teeth?		
Toothpaste and toothbrush	422	99.5
Chewing stick	2	0.5
Do you clean between your teeth?		
Yes	352	83.0
No	72	17.0
Total	424	100

Table 4.1: The oral hygiene habits of the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
What do you use to clean between your teeth?		
Toothpick	224	52.8
Dental floss	126	29.7
Thread	2	0.5
I do not use anything	72	17.0
Do you brush your teeth after eating snacks?		
Yes	362	85.4
No	62	14.6
Do you know what mouthwash is?		
Yes	258	60.8
No	166	39.2
Do you use mouthwash?		
Yes	248	58.5
No	176	41.5
What bristle strength of toothbrush do you use?		
Hard-strength bristle toothbrush	78	18.4
Medium-strength bristle toothbrush	114	34.0
Soft-strength bristle toothbrush	194	45.8
I do not know/Not applicable	8	1.9
Total	424	100

Table 4.2: The oral hygiene habits of the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
How often do you change your toothbrush in a year?		
Less than three months or every three months.	310	73.1
Longer than every three months	110	25.9
I do not know/Not applicable	4	1.0
What do you think will happen to your teeth if you do not brush your teeth regularly?		
Presence of mouth odour	106	25.0
Unpleasant, dirty teeth.	74	17.5
Tooth decay	196	46.2
Tooth loss	14	3.3
Toothache	24	5.7
Gum bleeding	2	0.5
I do not know	8	1.9
Total	424	100

Tables 4, 4.1, and 4.2 disclose that 422 (99.5%) of respondents brushed their teeth daily; meanwhile, 2 (0.5%) of respondents did not brush their teeth daily.

Meanwhile, with respect to the number of times respondents brushed their teeth daily, 246 (58.0%) of respondents brushed once, 172 (40.6%) brushed twice, whereas 6 (1.4%) of respondents brushed their teeth three times. Similarly, in relation to meals, 350 (82.5%) of respondents brushed their teeth before taking their meals, 12 (2.8%) brushed after taking their meals, while 62 (14.6%) of respondents brushed before having breakfast and after eating dinner. Also, 216 (50.9%) of respondents brushed for a duration of less than three minutes. Meanwhile, 208 (49.1%) brushed for a duration of three or more minutes.

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

From the point of view of the tool employed for toothbrushing, 422 (99.5%) of respondents made use of a toothbrush and toothpaste; meanwhile, 2 (0.5%) of respondents employed a chewing stick for the same purpose.

As far as the habit of cleaning in-between teeth is concerned, 352 (83.0) of respondents engaged in this habit, while 72 (17.0) of respondents did not engage in the habit of cleaning in-between teeth. Furthermore, from the respondents who engaged in the habit of cleaning in between the teeth, 224 (52.8%) employed the use of a toothpick, 126 (29.7%) made use of dental floss, and 2(0.5%) made use of a thread.

In addition, 414 (97.6%) of respondents reported having been taught by their teachers previously concerning proper oral hygiene practices; 10 (2.4%) of respondents, however, denied previously undertaking such education from their teachers. Besides, 362 (85.4%) of respondents brushed their teeth after consuming snacks; meanwhile, 62 (14.6%) did not brush their teeth after consuming snacks.

From the viewpoint of mouthwashes, 258 (60.8%) of respondents knew what a mouthwash was, while 166 (39.2%) did not know what a mouthwash was. Similarly, 248 (58.5%) of respondents used mouthwash; meanwhile, 176 (41.5%) did not employ the use of mouthwash.

About the type [strength] of toothbrushes used among the respondents, 78 (18.4%) of respondents used a hard-strength bristle toothbrush, 114 (34.0%) of respondents used a medium-strength bristle toothbrush, while 194 (45.8%) of respondents used a soft strength bristle toothbrush.

Correspondingly, concerning the frequency of toothbrush change, 310 (73.1%) of respondents changed their toothbrushes at less than or equal to every three months; meanwhile, 110 (25.9%) of respondents changed their toothbrushes greater than every three months.

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

Finally, on the expectations of respondents about the consequences of poor toothbrushing behaviour, 106 (25.0%) of respondents believed that mouth odour would become evident, 74 (17.5%) of respondents mentioned that the teeth would be dirty and unpleasant, 196 (46.2%) of respondents stated that tooth decay was the expected consequence, 40 (9.5%) of respondents raised tooth loss, toothache, and gum bleeding as potential results. Meanwhile, 8 (1.9%) of respondents had no idea.

Furthermore, the oral hygiene habit score for each of the scoreable responses on the questionnaire was totalled, and a descriptive analysis, showing the minimum, maximum, range, mean, standard deviation, median, and interquartile range across all the respondents, was computed [Table 5].

Moreover, the mean (SD) and median (IQR) oral hygiene habit scores were computed for distinct categories of each of the following variables: age [age group], gender, father's educational level, mother's educational level, and family composition [Table 5].

Table 5: The Oral hygiene habit scores among the respondents.

Oral hygiene habit scores among the respondents						
Min.	Max.	Range	Mean	SD	Median	IQR
2.50	8.33	5.83	5.33	1.13	5.50	1.50
Variable		Mean and Median Oral hygiene habit score				
Age group						
9 – 13		Mean (SD) = 5.35 (1.15); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.00, 4.50)				
14 – 17		Mean (SD) = 5.22 (0.94); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.50)				
Gender						
Male		Mean (SD) = 5.28 (1.27); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.17, 4.33)				
Female		Mean (SD) = 5.37 (0.99); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.00, 4.50)				
Father’s education level						
Primary		Mean (SD) = 5.11 (0.98); Median (IQR) = 5.25 (5.83, 4.21)				
Secondary		Mean (SD) = 5.51 (1.24); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.37, 4.50)				
Tertiary		Mean (SD) = 5.29 (1.08); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.67)				
Mother’s education level						
Primary		Mean (SD) = 5.20 (1.22); Median (IQR) = 5.00 (6.00, 4.00)				
Secondary		Mean (SD) = 5.42 (1.02); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.00, 4.50)				
Tertiary		Mean (SD) = 5.31 (1.19); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.50)				
Family composition						
Father and Mother		Mean (SD) = 5.33 (1.17); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.50)				
Mother only		Mean (SD) = 5.32 (1.10); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.33, 4.33)				
Father only		Mean (SD) = 5.22 (0.86); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (5.87, 4.75)				
Guardian		Mean (SD) = 5.49 (0.75); Median (IQR) = 5.67 (6.00, 4.83)				

*Min.: Minimum; Max.: Maximum; SD: Standard deviation; IQR: interquartile range (Q₃ – Q₁).

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

The mean (SD) median (IQR) oral hygiene habit score was also computed for distinct categories of each of the following variables: family size, number of children per household, birth rank, school type, and school location [Table 5.1].

Table 5.1: The Oral hygiene habit scores among the respondents.

Variable	Mean and Median Oral Hygiene Habit Scores
Family size	
2 – 5	Mean (SD) = 5.45 (0.95); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.33, 4.83)
6 – 10	Mean (SD) = 5.29 (1.20); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.00, 4.50)
11 – 14	Mean (SD) = 5.17 (0.99); Median (IQR) = 5.17 (6.00, 4.50)
Number of children per household	
1 – 4	Mean (SD) = 5.33 (1.20); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.33, 4.50)
5 – 8	Mean (SD) = 5.33 (1.03); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (5.83, 4.83)
9 – 12	Mean (SD) = 5.33 (0.68); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.00, 4.50)
Birth rank	
Firstborn	Mean (SD) = 5.45 (1.15); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.33, 4.79)
Second born	Mean (SD) = 5.17 (1.28); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.50)
Middle born	Mean (SD) = 5.37 (1.10); Median (IQR) = 5.42 (5.96, 4.50)
Last born	Mean (SD) = 5.29 (0.96); Median (IQR) = 5.41 (6.00, 4.71)
Only child	Mean (SD) = 4.50 (0.89); Median (IQR) = 4.50 (5.50, 3.50)
School type	
Public	Mean (SD) = 5.25 (1.09); Median (IQR) = 5.33 (6.00, 4.50)
Private	Mean (SD) = 5.44 (1.16); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.33, 4.50)
School location	
Egor	Mean (SD) = 5.54 (1.12); Median (IQR) = 5.50 (6.33, 4.83)
Oredo	Mean (SD) = 5.09 (1.08); Median (IQR) = 5.00 (5.83, 4.33)

* LGA: Local government area

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Tables 5 and 5.1 depict the oral hygiene habit scores, which is a measure of the level of oral hygiene among the respondents. The minimum knowledge/practice score was 2.50, and the maximum was 8.33, making the range among the respondents 5.83. Furthermore, the mean for this sample was 5.33 with a standard deviation of 1.13; meanwhile, the median was 5.50 with an interquartile range of 1.50.

The measures of central tendencies (mean and median) for the oral hygiene/practice score were as follows: the mean and median for the 9 – 13 age group were 5.35 and 5.50 as compared to 5.22 and 5.33 for the 14 – 17 age group.

Similarly, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores across the gender of the respondents were 5.28 and 5.33 for the male gender but 5.37 and 5.50 for the female gender.

In the same way, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores of respondents from the viewpoint of the father's education level were 5.11 and 5.25 for primary, 5.51 and 5.50 for secondary, and 5.29 and 5.33 for tertiary. Likewise, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores of respondents from the position of the mother's education level were 5.20 and 5.00 for primary, 5.42 and 5.50 for secondary, and 5.31 and 5.33 for tertiary.

Relatedly, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores of respondents from the perspective of family composition were 5.33 and 5.33 for respondents living with both parents, 5.32 and 5.50 for respondents living with a single parent (mother), and 5.22 and 5.33 for respondents living with a single parent (father). Meanwhile, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores were 5.49 and 5.67 for respondents living with their guardians.

The mean and median oral hygiene/practice score of the respondents from the standpoint of family size revealed a mean and median of 5.45 and 5.50 for a family size of 2 – 5 persons, a mean and

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median of 5.29 and 5.50 for a family size of 6 – 10 persons, and a mean and median of 5.17 and 5.17, respectively, for a family size of 11 – 14 persons.

In terms of the number of children per household of respondents, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores were 5.33 and 5.33 for a household with 1 – 4 children, 5.33 and 5.50 for a household with 5 – 8 children, and 5.33 and 5.50 for a household with 9 – 12 children, respectively.

As far as the birth rank of respondents is concerned, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores for firstborns were 5.45 and 5.50; for secondborns, 5.17 and 5.33; for middleborns, 5.37 and 5.42; for lastborns, 5.29 and 5.41, and lastly, for only children, 4.50 and 4.50, respectively.

From the point of view of school type, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores of respondents in public schools were 5.25 and 5.33, respectively. Meanwhile, the mean and median scores of respondents attending private schools were 5.44 and 5.50.

Correspondingly, from the viewpoint of school location, the mean and median oral hygiene/practice scores of respondents in Egor were 5.54 and 5.50. Meanwhile, the mean and median were 5.09 and 5.00 in Oredo.

Table 6: The oral hygiene habit categories among the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Oral hygiene habit category		
Poor	82	19.3
Fair	292	68.8
Good	50	11.8
Total	424	100

Table 6 highlights the oral hygiene habit categories among the studied respondents. Eighty-two or 19.3% of respondents were in the poor oral hygiene habit category, 292 (68.8%) of respondents were in the fair oral hygiene habit category, and 50 (11.8%) of respondents were in the good oral hygiene habit category.

4.2.3 SECTION C: THE LEVEL OF DENTAL SERVICES UTILISATION AMONG THE RESPONDENTS.

Table 7: Dental services utilisation among the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Have you had at least one dental visit within the following time frames?		
Yes, within the last one year	62	14.6
Yes, within the last three years	12	2.8
Yes, within the last five years	14	3.3
Yes, some time since I was born.	24	5.7
Never	312	73.6
Total	424	100

Table 7 divulges that 62 (14.6%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the last year; 12 (2.8%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the last three years, 14(3.3%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the last five years, 24 (5.7%) of respondents had utilised a dental service at some point since their birth; meanwhile, 312 (73.6%) of respondents had never utilised a dental service.

4.2.4 SECTION D: THE INFLUENCES AND PREDICTORS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABITS AMONG THE RESPONDENTS.

Table 8.0: The influences [motivations] of oral hygiene habits among respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to use what you use to brush your teeth?		
Parents	114	26.9
Mother	266	62.7
Father	40	9.4
Sibling	4	0.9
If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to use dental floss, toothpick, or thread?		
Parents	30	7.1
Mother	180	42.5
Father	128	30.2
Sibling	12	2.7
Friend	2	0.5
Not applicable	72	17.0
If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to brush your teeth after eating snacks?		
Parents	8	1.9
Parents	34	8.0
Mother	18	4.2
Father	364	85.8
Not applicable		
If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to use mouthwash?		
Parents	12	2.8
Father	46	10.8
Mother	98	23.1
Sibling	8	1.9
Cousins and Grandparents	10	2.4
Teacher/Media (Television)	4	1.0
Not applicable	246	58.0
Who (or what) advised your use of your present toothbrush?		
Parents	94	22.2
Father	82	19.3
Mother	238	56.1
Sibling	4	0.9
Friend	4	0.9
Media (Television)	2	0.5
Total	424	100

Table 8.1: The influences [motivations] of oral hygiene habits among respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
From whom or where did you adopt the duration of changing your toothbrush?		
Parents	40	9.4
Father	126	29.7
Mother	228	53.8
Sibling/Grandparents	10	2.3
Teacher	18	4.2
Dentist	2	0.5
Has anyone close to you ever praised or scolded you for brushing/not brushing regularly?		
Yes	400	94.3
No	24	5.7
Who praised/scolded you?		
Parents	66	15.6
Father	58	13.7
Mother	176	41.5
Sibling	50	11.8
Grandparents	2	0.5
Friend	34	8.0
Teacher	12	2.7
Neighbour at home	2	0.5
Not applicable	24	5.7
Total	424	100

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Table 8 shows that in terms of the influences of the respondents' toothbrushing habit, 114 (26.9%) of respondents cited both parents, 266 (62.7%) of respondents referenced their mothers, 40 (9.4%) of respondents referred to their fathers, while 4(0.9%) of respondents mentioned their siblings.

For the influences in-between teeth cleaning habits of the respondents, 30 (7.1%) of respondents had both parents as influences, 180 (42.5%) of respondents had their mother; 128 (30.2%) of respondents had their fathers, 12 (2.7%), their siblings, while 2 (0.5%) of respondents had their friends.

The major influences among the respondents for the habit of brushing their teeth after consuming snacks were the parents, in 8 (1.9%) of respondents; fathers, in 18 (4.2%) of respondents; and mothers, in 34 (8.0%) of respondents.

Regarding the habit of mouthwash use, the prime influences among the respondents were the parents, in 12 (2.8%) of respondents; fathers, in 46 (10.8%) of respondents; mothers, in 98 (23.1%) of respondents; siblings, in 8 (1.9%) of respondents; Cousins and Grandparents, in 10 (2.4%) of respondents, and Teachers and the media 4 (1.0%) of respondents.

Furthermore, on the type [strength] of toothbrushes used among respondents, choices of toothbrushes used were advised by parents in 94 (22.2%) of respondents, fathers in 82 (19.3%) of respondents; mothers, in 238 (56.1%) of respondents, and the siblings, friends and media, in 10 (2.3%) of respondents.

In addition, 40 (9.4%) of respondents adopted the duration for changing their toothbrushes from their parents, 126 (29.7%) respondents from their fathers, 228 (53.8%) respondents from their

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mothers; 10 (2.3%) of respondents, from their siblings and grandparents; 18 (4.2%) of respondents, from their teachers, and 2 (0.5%) from their dentist.

Finally, with respect to positive and negative reinforcements of toothbrushing behaviours among the respondents, 400 (94.3%) of respondents reported being praised or scolded for brushing or not brushing regularly. Meanwhile, 24 (5.7%) of respondents did not report being praised or scolded for brushing or not brushing regularly. More so, individuals that either praised or scolded respondents included parents in 66 (15.6%) of respondents, fathers in 58 (13.7%) of respondents, mothers in 176 (41.5%) of respondents, siblings in 50 (11.8%) of respondents, friends, in 34(8%) of respondents, teachers, in 12 (2.7%) of respondents, and grandparents and neighbours at home in 4 (1.0%) of respondents.

The assumption of normality for the data of a particular variable of interest must be met before deciding whether a parametric or non-parametric inferential test is to be applied. Thus, the outcome variable for this study, oral hygiene habits of the respondents, recorded as a score or continuous variable of measurement, was subjected to several normality testing analyses, including the following: a histogram, stem and leaf plot, QQ plot and detrended QQ plot, box and whisker plot, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and the Shapiro-Wilk's test.

Figure 4: Histogram of the outcome variable showing a bell curve fitted in.

Figure 4 suggests a normal distribution of the variable 'oral hygiene habit' among the respondents.

Figure 7: Detrended QQ plot of the outcome variable.

Figure 7 suggests a non-normal distribution of the variable ‘oral hygiene habit’ among the respondents.

Figure 8: Box plot of the outcome variable

Figure 8 suggests a non-normal distribution of the variable ‘oral hygiene habit’ among the respondents.

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Oral_hygiene_habit_score	.067	424	.000	.991	424	.011

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Figure 9: Normality tests for the outcome variable

Figure 9 suggests a non-normal distribution of the variable ‘oral hygiene habit’ among the respondents (Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic $\cong 0.07$, $p < 0.01$; Shapiro-Wilk’s statistic = 0.99, $p < 0.02$).

In conclusion, taking into account suggestions of the histogram, stem and leaf plot, QQ plot and detrended QQ plot, box and whisker plot, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and the Shapiro-Wilk’s test, non-parametric inferential tests were applied to the outcome variable ‘oral hygiene habit’.

Table 9.0: The predictors of oral hygiene habits and the oral hygiene habit categories among the respondents.

Variables			Significance (Chi-squared) testing	
Oral hygiene habit category		Age group		
	9 – 13 years	14 – 17 years	$\chi^2 = 7.02,$ $df = 2,$ $p < 0.031.$	
Poor	74	8		
Fair	256	36		
Good	50	0		
Oral hygiene habit category		School type		
	Public	Private	$\chi^2 = 13.24,$ $df = 2,$ $p < 0.002.$	
Poor	44	38		
Fair	174	118		
Good	16	34		
Oral hygiene habit category		School location		
	Egor	Oredo	$\chi^2 = 11.32,$ $df = 2,$ $p < 0.004.$	
Poor	32	50		
Fair	160	132		
Good	34	15		
Oral hygiene habit category		Family size		
	2 – 5 persons	6 – 10 persons	11 – 14 persons	$\chi^2 = 8.17,$ $df = 4,$ $p > 0.084.$
Poor	8	66	8	
Fair	30	222	40	
Good	0	46	4	

*df: degree of freedom.

Table 9.1: The predictors of oral hygiene habits and the oral hygiene habit categories among the respondents.

Variables						Significance (Chi-squared) testing
Birth rank						
Oral hygiene habit category	First child	Second born	Middle born	Last born	Only child	Fisher's exact statistic = 12.97, df = 8, p > 0.11.
Poor	28	16	22	14	2	
Fair	80	50	96	62	4	
Good	22	6	18	4	0	
Father's education level						
Oral hygiene habit category	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary			
Poor	22	24	36	$\chi^2 = 12.18,$		
Fair	56	98	138	$df = 4,$		
Good	2	24	24	$p < 0.017.$		
Mother's education level						
Oral hygiene habit category	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary			
Poor	24	24	34	$\chi^2 = 11.35,$		
Fair	50	134	108	$df = 4,$		
Good	8	18	24	$p < 0.024.$		
Number of children per household						
Oral hygiene habit category	1 – 4 Children	5 – 8 Children	9 – 12 Children			
Poor	60	22	0	Fisher's exact statistic = 13.09,		
Fair	158	128	6	$df = 4,$		
Good	36	14	0	$p < 0.005.$		

*Fisher's exact test was reported when the expected count assumptions for the chi-squared test were not satisfied; df: degree of freedom

Table 9.2: The predictors of oral hygiene habits and the oral hygiene categories among the respondents

Variables		Significance (Chi-squared) testing			
Oral hygiene habit category	Gender				
	Male	Female			
Poor	50	32		$\chi^2 = 25.31,$ $df = 2,$ $p < 0.01.$	
Fair	110	182			
Good	34	16			
Oral hygiene habit category	Family composition				
	Father and Mother	Mother only	Father only	Guardian	
Poor	64	14	2	2	Fisher's exact* statistic = 14.18, $df = 6,$ $p < 0.021.$
Fair	228	26	16	22	
Good	46	4	0	0	

*Fisher's exact test was reported when the expected count assumptions for the chi-squared test were not satisfied; df: degree of freedom.

Tables 9.1, 9.2, and 9.3 outline the notable predictor variables among the respondents. These variables included age [age group], school type, school location, family size, birth rank, father's education level, mother's education level, number of children per household, gender, and family composition.

Predictor variables such as age [age group], school type, school location, father's education level, mother's education level, number of children per household, gender, and family composition were discovered to be significantly associated with the oral hygiene habits of the respondents ($p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, predictor variables such as birth rank and family size were revealed not to be significantly associated with the oral hygiene habits of the respondents ($p > 0.05$).

4.2.5 SECTION E: RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀ 1: Parental educational level is not a predictor of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

Table 10: Multinomial logistic regression showing the ability of parental education level to predict the oral hygiene habits of respondents.

Variable	OR	95% C. I.	P- value	Decision
Fair oral hygiene habit category				
Father's educational level				
Primary	0.73	0.32, 1.69	> 0.46	Fail to reject H ₀
Secondary	0.98	0.51, 1.89	> 0.94	Fail to reject H ₀
Tertiary*	1	-	-	
Mother's education level				
Primary	0.79	0.34, 1.84	> 0.59	Fail to reject H ₀
Secondary	1.88	0.98, 3.60	> 0.055	Fail to reject H ₀
Tertiary*	1	-	-	
Good oral hygiene habit category				
Father's educational level				
Primary	0.15	0.03, 0.86	< 0.034	Reject H ₀
Secondary	1.53	0.64, 3.64	> 0.34	Fail to reject H ₀
Tertiary*	1	-	-	
Mother's education level				
Primary	0.84	0.26, 2.78	> 0.77	Fail to reject H ₀
Secondary	1.14	0.47, 2.76	> 0.77	Fail to reject H ₀
Tertiary*	1	-	-	

*Reference category; OR: Odds ratio; 95% C. I.: 95% confidence interval.

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Table 10 shows that respondents with fathers having a primary level of education were 27% less likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with fathers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.46$).

Likewise, respondents with fathers having a secondary level of education were 2% less likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with fathers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.94$).

Similarly, respondents with fathers having a primary level of education were 85% less likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with fathers having a tertiary level of education ($p < 0.034$).

Meanwhile, respondents with fathers with a secondary level of education were 53% more likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with fathers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.34$).

On the other hand, respondents with mothers with a primary level of education were 21% less likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with mothers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.59$).

Likewise, respondents with mothers with a secondary level of education were 88% more likely to have good fair hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with mothers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.055$).

Relatedly, respondents with mothers having a primary level of education were 16% less likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with mothers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.77$).

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In a similar way, respondents with mothers having a secondary level of education were 14% more likely to have good hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts with mothers having a tertiary level of education ($p > 0.77$).

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H₀ 2: Predictors such as age, gender, number of children per household, family composition, school type and school location are not significant predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

Table 11: Multinomial logistic regression showing the ability of gender, school type and school location to predict the oral hygiene habits of respondents.

Variable	OR	95% C. I.	P- value	Decision
Fair oral hygiene habit category				
Gender				
Male	0.37	0.22, 0.62	< 0.001	Reject H ₀
Female*	1	-	-	
School type				
Public	1.18	0.71, 1.96	> 0.51	Fail to reject H ₀
Private*	1	-	-	
School location				
Egor	1.99	1.20, 3.33	< 0.007	Reject H ₀
Oredo*	1	-	-	
Good oral hygiene habit category				
Gender				
Male	1.15	0.54, 2.46	> 0.72	Fail to reject H ₀
Female*	1	-	-	
School type				
Public	0.39	0.18, 0.82	< 0.014	Reject H ₀
Private*	1	-	-	
School location				
Egor	3.41	1.60, 7.62	< 0.002	Reject H ₀
Oredo*	1	-	-	

*Reference category; OR: Odds ratio; 95% C. I.: 95% confidence interval.

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Table 11 discloses that male respondents were 63% less likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their female counterparts ($p < 0.001$).

Meanwhile, respondents attending public schools were 18% more likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their private school counterparts ($p > 0.51$).

In a similar vein, respondents in Egor local government area were 99% more likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts in Oredo local government area ($p < 0.007$).

On the other hand, male respondents were 15% more likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their female counterparts ($p > 0.72$).

Meanwhile, respondents attending public schools were 61% less likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their private school counterparts ($p < 0.014$).

Similarly, respondents in Egor local government area were 3.4 times more likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts in Oredo local government area ($p < 0.002$).

Table 12: Multinomial logistic regression showing the ability of age, number of children per household, and family composition to predict the oral hygiene habits of respondents.

Variable	OR	95% C. I.	P- value	Decision
Fair oral hygiene habit category				
Age	1.21	1.02, 1.44	< 0.028	Reject H ₀
Number of children per household	1.04	0.89, 1.23	> 0.60	Fail to reject H ₀
Family composition				
Father and Mother	1.00	0.55, 1.81	> 0.99	Fail to reject H ₀
Others*	1	-	-	
Good oral hygiene habit category				
Age	0.86	0.65, 1.12	> 0.25	Fail to reject H ₀
Number of children per household	1.00	0.79, 1.28	> 0.97	Fail to reject H ₀
Family composition				
Father and Mother	3.23	1.03, 10.19	< 0.046	Reject H ₀
Others*	1	-	-	

*Others: Mother only, Father only, and Guardian; *Reference category; OR: Odds ratio; 95% C. I.: 95% confidence interval.

Table 12 reveals that respondents with a one-year increase in age were 21 % more likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits ($p < 0.028$).

Similarly, with an increase in the number of children per household by 1, respondents were 4% more likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits ($p > 0.60$)

Likewise, respondents living with both parents were as likely to have fair oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts living with their father only, mother only, or guardian (> 0.99)

On the other hand, with a one-year increase in age, respondents were 14 % less likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits ($p > 0.25$).

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Similarly, with an increase in the number of children per household by 1, respondents were neither more likely nor less likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits ($p > 0.97$)

Likewise, respondents living with both parents were 3.23 times more likely to have good oral hygiene habits than poor oral hygiene habits compared to their counterparts living with their father only, mother only, or guardian ($p > 0.046$).

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS, SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the discussion of findings, the implications of the findings to public health practice, the summary of the study, limitations of the study, conclusions, recommendations, and suggestions for further studies.

5.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Oral hygiene entails the measures taken to keep the mouth clean, thereby promoting oral health and preventing the development of oral diseases. Thus, the uptake of an adequate oral hygiene habit for the growing schoolchild cannot be understated if the schoolchild is to be oral disease-free. The consolidation of a proper oral hygiene routine for the schoolchild depends on the presence of individual, social, and environmental factors or predictors. This study assessed the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC

In the present study, the age of the respondents ranged from 9 – 17 years, with a mean (SD) of 11.48 (1.68) years and a median (IQR) of 11.00 (12.00, 10.00) years, respectively. Meanwhile, more than two-fifths of the sample were males, while more than one-half were females. These findings agreed with those of Oyedele et al. (2019), who reported an age range of 8 – 16 years, with more than two-fifths of respondents being male and more than one-half being females. Meanwhile, the age findings of the present study also agree with those of Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who discovered an age range of 7 – 17 years among the studied respondents. However, the gender

findings of the present study disagreed with those of Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who reported more than two-fifths of respondents being female and more than one-half being male. The age range findings were also at variance with those of Al Trabelsi et al. (2015), who reported an age range of 9 – 12 among respondents; meanwhile, in terms of gender, the findings of the present study aligned with those of Al Trabelsi et al. (2015) with more than two-fifths of respondents in their study being male, and more than one-half, being females.

Also, the educational level of fathers of most respondents was tertiary as compared to secondary and primary, a finding that corroborated those of Al Trabelsi et al. (2015), who discovered that three-fifths of respondents' fathers had a tertiary level of education compared to one-fifth that had secondary level of education, and less than one-fifth of fathers that had a primary level of education. The findings of the present study, however, contrasted with those of Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who reported that less than one-tenth of the respondents' fathers in their study had a tertiary level of education as compared to four-tenths of fathers who had a secondary level of education and three-tenths of fathers that had a primary level of education.

Likewise, the educational level of mothers of most respondents was secondary as compared to tertiary and primary, a finding that agreed with those of Al Trabelsi et al. (2015), who noted that forty-eight percent of respondents' mothers had a secondary level of education compared to forty-seven percent having a tertiary level of education and three percent of respondents mothers having a primary level of education. The present findings also corroborate those of Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who reported that forty-six percent of respondents' mothers had a secondary level of education compared to forty-two percent of respondents' mothers who had a primary level of education, and eleven percent of mothers that had no form of education.

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The most common birth rank among the sampled respondents was middleborns in three-tenths of the respondents, closely followed by firstborns in three-tenths of respondents, lastborns, secondborns, and finally, only children. This finding was akin to those of Oyedele et al. (2019), who reported four-tenths of their study's respondents as others [middleborns], three-tenths of the respondents as firstborns, and two-tenths of their studied respondents as lastborns.

In the same way, a majority of respondents belonged to families having three to four children, a finding that might be a reflection of the values on offspring number among the residents in the studied environment.

Also, more than two-fifths of the respondents belonged to families with sizes of six to seven persons, a finding that could be attributed to the value system on family size held by residents in the studied environment.

Furthermore, about four-fifths of respondents belonged to families consisting of a father and a mother, a finding that agreed with those of Oyedele et al. (2019), who reported eighty-one percent of respondents living with both parents. These findings possibly are expressions of the ethno-religious background of the residents of the studied environments.

In addition, over one-half of respondents attended public schools, and more than one-half of respondents attended schools located in the Egor local government area. These findings reflect the sampling technique utilised for the present study.

LEVELS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABIT

In this study, almost all the respondents brushed their teeth daily; a majority of respondents brushed their teeth once daily, while two-fifths of respondents brushed twice daily. These findings are in tandem with those of Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who reported that over three-fifths of

respondents in their study brushed once daily compared to more than one-tenth of respondents who brushed their teeth twice or more times daily; less than one-tenth of respondents did not brush daily. The findings in the present study misaligned with those of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that three-fifths of the respondents in their study brushed twice or more times daily as compared to about two-fifths of respondents brushing once daily. The findings of this study were also at variance with those of Elkhodary et al. (2023), who reported that four-tenth of respondents in their study brushed once daily while over three-tenth of respondents brushed twice or more times daily; over two-tenth of respondents did not brush their teeth daily.

Similarly, a majority of respondents brushed their teeth before meals, a discovery that corroborated that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that ninety-three percent of respondents in their study brushed before meals in comparison to seven percent of their studied respondents who brushed after meals.

Likewise, more respondents brushed their teeth for less than three minutes as compared to three minutes or more, a finding that was at variance with that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that thirty-two percent of respondents in their study brushed for less than three minutes compared to sixty-seven percent who brushed for three minutes or more.

The employed tooth-cleaning tool among almost all the studied respondents was the toothbrush and toothpaste, a finding that concurs with that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that toothbrushes and toothpaste were used in about ninety-six percent of the respondents in their study. The present study's findings also agreed with those of Kuppuswamy et al. (2014), who reported that toothbrushes and toothpaste were used by about ninety-seven percent of the respondents in their study.

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More so, more than four-fifths of respondents cleaned in-between their teeth, a finding that contrasts that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that more than four-fifths of the respondents in their study did not clean in-between their teeth. Besides, the tool employed for in-between teeth cleaning by more than five-tenths of the respondents was a toothpick or another device, such as the thread, as compared to about three-tenths of respondents who used dental floss. This finding agrees with that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that over nine-tenths of the respondents in their study utilised the toothpick, broomstick, thread, and matchstick, as compared to less than one-tenth of respondents who used dental floss.

In addition, more than four-fifths of respondents brushed their teeth after consuming snacks, and another three-fifths knew what a mouthwash was, findings that may be linked to their parental education levels.

More than half of respondents also utilised a mouthwash, and a majority used either soft or medium bristle toothbrushes, findings that might be hinged on the social structure of the studied sample.

Similarly, a majority of respondents changed their toothbrushes less than or every three months, a finding that agrees with that of Lawal et al. (2022), who reported that eighty-four percent of the respondents in their study changed their toothbrushes before three months as compared to sixteen percent of respondents that changed their toothbrush after three months. The present study's finding, however, disagreed with Akinyamoju et al. (2020), who reported that fifteen percent of the respondents in their study changed their toothbrushes once every three months compared to eighty-five percent of respondents who changed their toothbrushes after three months. The present study's findings were also at variance with those of Punitha and Sivaprakasam (2011), who reported that more than seventy percent of respondents changed their toothbrushes after three

months. The differences in the findings of these studies may be attributed to the differences in the level of socioeconomic development of the studied environments.

On the consequences of poor oral hygiene habits, a majority of respondents cited tooth decay, mouth odour, and poor aesthetic appearance, a finding that hints at the expectation construct of the studied respondents.

Finally, more than six-tenths of respondents had fair oral hygiene habits; next were almost two-tenths of respondents who had poor oral hygiene habits; meanwhile, one-tenth of respondents had good oral hygiene habits.

LEVEL OF DENTAL SERVICE UTILISATION

In the present study, more than seven-tenths of respondents had never visited a dental service provider previously, and a bare one-tenths of respondents visited a service provider within the last year. These findings were in tandem with those of Mohammed et al. (2023), who reported an annual dental service utilisation of about eleven percent among the respondents in their study; Denloye et al. (2010), who reported a lifetime dental service utilisation of about fourteen percent, and Eigbobo and Obianuju (2016), who reported an annual dental service utilisation of twenty-one percent among the respondents in their study. The present study's findings, however, disagreed with that of Finlayson et al. (2018), who reported an annual dental service utilisation of sixty-six percent among their study's respondents; the discrepancy between these findings could be due to differences in the level of socioeconomic development in the studied environments.

INFLUENCES AND PREDICTORS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABIT

In this study, mothers influenced toothbrushing tool use in three-fifths of respondents, both parents in one-fifth, and fathers/siblings in the remaining one-fifth. This finding underscores a mother's prime role in the family. Mothers also influenced in-between teeth cleaning in two-fifths

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of respondents, while fathers influenced three-tenths, highlighting observational learning due to increased mother-child interaction. More than half of respondents who brushed after snacking and used mouthwash were influenced by their mothers, reflecting mothers as the primary source of learning. Similarly, mothers influenced the choice of toothbrush type and duration for changing toothbrushes in more than half of respondents, emphasizing mothers' role in purchasing oral hygiene products and guiding the family's oral hygiene habits. About two-fifths mentioned mothers as positive/negative reinforcers of their oral hygiene habits, pointing to a mother's role as the first teacher.

Additionally, respondents' oral hygiene habits were significantly associated with age, school type, school location, parents' education levels, number of children per household, gender, and family composition. In comparison to the tertiary level of education, the primary level of education for a father was a significant predictor of good oral hygiene habits, with respondents of the former group being less likely to have good oral hygiene habits compared to the latter. School type was also a significant predictor for good oral hygiene habits, with public school attendees less likely to have good habits compared to private school attendees. Besides, family composition predicted good oral hygiene habits, with respondents raised by both parents having higher odds compared to those raised by single parents or guardians, a finding that aligns with the report of Oyedele et al. (2019), who noticed a thirty-three percent chance of having good oral hygiene habits with the former group than the latter.

Age predicted fair oral hygiene habits, with respondents having a twenty percent chance of having fair oral hygiene habits with each one-year increase in age. Gender also predicted fair oral hygiene habits, with males being less likely to be in this category than females. In addition, school location

predicted both fair and good oral hygiene habits, with pupils in Egor LGA having higher odds for both categories of oral hygiene habits compared to those in Oredo.

Conversely, birth rank and family size were not significantly associated with oral hygiene habits. Age, all levels of mother's education, and gender did not predict good oral hygiene habits, which contrasted with Oyedele et al. (2019), who found age and gender to be significant predictors of good habits. The number of children per household did not predict both fair and good oral hygiene habits.

5.2 IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS FOR PUBLIC HEALTH PRACTICE

Primarily, the findings from this study revealed that the fair oral hygiene habit category was the most prevailing among primary schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State. Besides, mothers were shown to be the most influential in the adoption of oral habits by schoolchildren in the study sample.

Furthermore, the primary level of education of fathers predicted good oral hygiene habits among respondents. Age, gender, and school location predicted fair oral hygiene habits among the respondents; meanwhile, school type and, school location, family composition predicted good oral hygiene habits among respondents.

These findings cite the need for a more robust government-initiated oral health education and promotion campaign involving interactions with schoolchildren and social predictors such as mothers, fathers, the local environment, and schoolteachers.

5.3 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The first limitation of the present study was its restriction to only the schoolchildren population in the final year of primary education.

Second, the study findings may differ from those of a similar age grade in a different study environment because of variations in the values and social characteristics of the respondents.

Third, the study was undertaken within a short period, which made it impossible for the researcher to investigate on a larger scale.

Fourth, the socioeconomic status of the parents of respondents was not included as a predictor variable; this was due to the difficulty encountered with gaining information on the monthly income of the parents of the respondents in this study; the educational level of both parents, which is a good indicator of the parental social class was, however, included.

Finally, not every construct of the theoretical framework was captured in this study and therefore, generalising the findings in this domain should be done with caution. This study, nevertheless, has provided an invaluable understanding of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.

5.4 SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

This inquiry was a cross-sectional observational school-based study that assessed the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State. The instrument for data collection was a semi-structured questionnaire comprising both open and closed-ended questions with a reliability of 0.735. IBM SPSS version 25 was utilised for entering and analysing entered data.

The following were the main findings: 82 (19.3%) of respondents had poor oral hygiene habits, 292 (68.8%) of respondents had fair oral hygiene, and 50 (11.8%) of respondents had good oral hygiene habits.

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Also, 62 (14.6%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the last year; 12 (2.8%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the previous three years, 14(3.3%) of respondents had utilised a dental service within the last five years, 24 (5.7%) of respondents had utilised a dental service at some point since their birth; meanwhile, 312 (73.6%) of respondents had never utilised a dental service.

In addition, mothers were, in the majority, the key influencers to oral hygiene habit uptake across the oral hygiene habits categories of the respondents.

The present study revealed that the oral hygiene habits of respondents were significantly associated with the respondents' age, school type, school location, father's education level, mother's education level, number of children per household, gender, and family composition ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, the oral hygiene habits of respondents were not significantly associated with respondents' birth rank and family size ($p > 0.05$).

Furthermore, gender, age, and school location were significant predictors of fair oral hygiene habits among the respondents ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, the primary level of the father's education, school type, school location, and family composition were significant predictors of good oral hygiene habits among respondents ($p < 0.05$).

5.5 CONCLUSION

This study's findings revealed that a substantial portion of schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State, exhibited fair oral hygiene habits. The utilization of dental services among these schoolchildren, however, was found to be poor. Mothers were, notably, identified as the primary influencers of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren. Gender, age, school type, school location,

the primary level of the respondents' fathers' education, and family composition were all significant predictors of oral hygiene habits in this population.

Recommendations include enhancing oral health education and promotion campaigns through various media channels such as radio, television, and school visits. These efforts, which the Edo State Ministry of Health should facilitate, are expected to improve oral hygiene knowledge and subsequently foster better habits among schoolchildren.

5.6 RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the outcomes of the present study, the considerations and implications drawn from it, the following recommendations were made:

1. Policy initiatives should focus on enhancing the capabilities of healthcare providers, especially dental and public health professionals. This capability enhancement intervention includes capacity-building measures to equip them with the necessary skills and resources to promote good oral hygiene practices effectively.
2. There should be an escalation of mass media campaigns aimed at raising awareness about oral health and hygiene. Additionally, initiating school visits can serve as a valuable intervention to educate the community and encourage the adoption of healthy oral hygiene habits.

5.7 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further, mixed methods research is needed to gain a more complete and holistic understanding of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among this study population.

REFERENCES

- Abate, B., Ephrem, M., Gebremariam, M., Ayalew, Y., & Shimels, T. (2020).** Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices towards Oral Hygiene among Students of Medhanealem High School, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Journal of Dental Research and Review*, 7(2), 42-49. |DOI: 10.4103/jdr.jdr_6_20
- Aguilar-Polo, A., & Mateo-Solis, M. (2021).** Knowledge of oral health and oral hygiene habits of college students. *Journal of Oral Research*, 10(3), 1-6.
- Ahmad, V. N., Hazman, N., Razali, A. S., Rasdi, Z., & Zulkapli, R. (2019).** Practices, Attitudes, and Awareness Of Suburban Adolescence School Children Towards Oral Hygiene: School-Based Survey: *Journal of Health and Translational Medicine (JUMMEC)*, 22(2), 56-63.
- Akaji, E. A., Ikechebelu, Q. U., & Osadolor, O. O. (2020).** Assessing dental caries and related factors in 12-year-old Nigerian school children: Report from a Southeastern State. *European Journal of General Dentistry*, 9(01), 11-16.
- Akinyamoju, A. O., Adeoye, I. A., Akinyamoju, A. O., & Dairo, D. M. (2020).** Oral health knowledge and practice: Influence of socio-demographic factors in rural Nigerian school children. *African Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 49(2), 215-223.
- AlGhamdi, A.S., Almarghlani, A.A., Alyafi, R.A., Kayal, R.A., & Al-Zahrani, M.S. (2020).** Gingival health and oral hygiene practices among high school children in Saudi Arabia. *Annals of Saudi Medicine*, 40, 126 - 135.

AlMalki, T., Bagazi, F., Hejazi, A., Khalid, N., & Ansari, S. (2020). Attitudes and Hygiene Practices towards Toothbrush Use among Saudi College Students; A Survey-based Study. *Donnish Journal of Dentistry and Oral Hygiene*, 6(1), 021-030

Alshloul, M. N. (2023). Oral health knowledge, attitude, and practice among school children in Abha-Saudi Arabia. *The Journal of School Nursing*, 39(4), 295-304.

Atarbashi-Moghadam, F., & Atarbashi-Moghadam, S. (2018). Tooth brushing in children. *Journal of Dental Materials and Techniques*, 7(4), 181-184.

Al Agili, D. E., & Farsi, N. J. (2020). Need for dental care drives utilisation of dental services among children in Saudi Arabia. *International Dental Journal*, 70(3), 183-192.

Al Trabelsi, N. A., Juni, M. H., & Huda, B. Z. (2015). Predictors of oral hygiene practices among primary school children of Alzintan city, Libya. *International Journal of Public Health and Clinical Sciences*, 2(6), 68-82.

Batinić, M., Bašić, R., & Kolarić, S. (2020). Influence of dietary habits on oral hygiene in children. *Paediatrica Croatica*, 64(1), 28-33.

Balaji, V. R., Niazi, T. M., & Dhanasekaran, M. (2019). An unusual presentation of dental calculus. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*, 23(5), 484-486.
https://doi.org/10.4103/jisp.jisp_680_18

Badarch, J., Batbaatar, S., & Paulik, E. (2021). Prevalence and Correlates of Poor Oral Hygiene among School-Going Students in Mongolia. *Dentistry Journal*, 9(2), 12.

Bashirian, S., Seyedzadeh-Sabounchi, S., Shirahmadi, S., Soltanian, A. R., Karimi-Shahanjarini, A., & Vahdatinia, F. (2018). Socio-demographic determinants as predictors of

oral hygiene status and gingivitis in schoolchildren aged 7-12 years old: A cross-sectional study. *PLoS One*, 13(12), e0208886.

Ben-Amos, P., G. (2018). Edo. *Encyclopedia of World Cultures*.
<https://www.encyclopedia.com/humanities/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/edo>

Berk, L. E. (2018). *Child Development* (10th ed.). Pearson.

Bhuiyan, M. A., Anwar, H. B., Anwar, R. B., Ali, M. N., & Agrawal, P. (2020). Oral Hygiene Awareness and Practices among a Sample of Primary School Children in Rural Bangladesh. *Dentistry journal*, 8(2), 36. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj8020036>

Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. (2023). Edo. *Encyclopedia Britannica*.
<https://www.britannica.com/place/Edo-state-Nigeria>

Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. (2023b). Benin City. *Encyclopedia Britannica*.
<https://www.britannica.com/place/Benin-City>

Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. (2023). Predictor. The Britannica Dictionary. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/predictor>

Cabrera, M. F., Pillacela, J. F., Lafebre, M. F., Reinoso, J. D. C., & Ramón, J. E. (2022). Impact of an educational intervention on oral health in children aged 8 to 11 years. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 14(2), 510-514.

Chen, Q., Kong, Y., Gao, W., & Mo, L. (2018). Effects of socioeconomic status, parent-child relationship, and learning motivation on reading ability. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1297.

- Chen, W., Chan, T. W., Wong, L. H., Looi, C. K., Liao, C. C., Cheng, H. N., ... & Pi, Z. (2020).** IDC theory: habit and the habit loop. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 15(1), 1-19.
- Chua, D. R., Hu, S., Sim, Y. F., Lim, W., Lai, B. W. P., & Hong, C. H. L. (2022).** At what age do children have the motor development to adequately brush their teeth?. *International journal of paediatric dentistry*, 32(4), 598–606. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ipd.12938>
- Dagnew, Z. A., Abraham, I. A., Beraki, G. G., Tesfamariam, E. H., Mittler, S., & Tesfamichael, Y. Z. (2020).** Nurses' attitude towards oral care and their practicing level for hospitalized patients in Orotta National Referral Hospital, Asmara-Eritrea: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Nursing*, 19, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-020-00457-3>
- Deng, L., Cai, T., Li, Y. H., Zhou, Z., & Yang, Z. Y. (2019).** Tooth brushing behavior and its influencing factors among middle school students in Chongqing, China. *Int J Clin Exp Med*, 12(7), 8957-8963.
- Denloye, O., Ajayi, D., Bankole, O., & Bamidele, P. (2010).** Dental service utilization among junior secondary school students in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Pediatric Dental Journal*, 20(2), 177-181. https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/pdj/20/2/20_2_177/_pdf
- Devi, B., Pradhan, S., Giri, D., & Baxodirovna, N. L. (2022).** Concept of Social cognitive theory and its application in the field of Medical and Nursing education: a framework to guide Research. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 5161-5168.
- Dhage, V. S., & Chougule, P. (2019).** Importance of oral hygiene in oro-dental diseases: A review study. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 6(12), 69-74.

Dikshit, P., Limbu, S., Gupta, S., & Pradhan, R. (2018). Evaluation of knowledge, attitude and practices of parents toward their children's oral health compared with their dental caries status.

Birat Journal of Health Sciences, 3(2), 447-452.

Doley, S., & Srivastava, M. (2021). Oral hygiene status and its association with oral hygiene practices among school going children of rural and urban areas in Kamrup district, Assam.

International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health, 8(5), 2245.

Duangthip, D., & Chu, C. H. (2020). Challenges in oral hygiene and oral health policy. *Frontiers in Oral Health*, 1, 575428.

Edo State Ministry of Education. (2016). *2016 Public and private primary and secondary school enrolment by sex and local government area*, unpublished raw data.

Eigbobo, J. O., & Obiajunwa, C. C. (2016). Utilization of dental services among secondary school students in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *European Journal of General Dentistry*, 5(02), 74-79.

Elkhodary, H. M., Abdelnabi, M. H., Swelem, A. A., Sabbagh, H. J., El Meligy, O. A. E. S., Talaat, I. M., ... & El Tantawi, M. (2023). Individual, familial and country-level factors associated with oral hygiene practices in children: an international survey. *BMC Oral Health*, 23(1), 50.

Ellakany, P., Madi, M., Fouda, S. M., Ibrahim, M., & AlHumaid, J. (2021). The effect of parental education and socioeconomic status on dental caries among Saudi children. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(22), 11862.

Elzahaf, R. A., Elzer, A. S., & Edwebi, S. (2019). Oral health practices, knowledge, and attitudes among primary schoolchildren in Derna City, Libya: A cross-sectional survey. *International Journal of Pedodontic Rehabilitation*, 4(2), 41.

Fadare, A. S., Daniel, B. P., Fadare, C. M., & Adamu, V. E. (2021). Oral health knowledge and practices among elementary pupils attending Saint Louis College, City of San Fernando, La Union, The Philippines. *Orapuh Journal*, 2(2), e812-e812.

Federal Ministry of Education. (2023) Edo State School Lis, Open Education Data. Available at <http://fmebasic.intellisys.xyz/index.php/states-stats/edo/33-states/edo/150-edo-state-basic-schools-list>

Ferizi, L., Bimbashi, V., Kelmendi, J., & Olloni, T. (2020). Oral health status among 12-year-old schoolchildren in Kosovo. *Pesquisa Brasileira em Odontopediatria e Clínica Integrada*, 20.

Finlayson, T. L., Chuang, E., Baek, J. D., & Seidman, R. (2018). Dental service utilization among children in the child welfare system. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 22, 753-761.

Fomete, B., & Adebayo, E. T. (2018). Review Of Dentistry in West Africa- Challenges and Prospects. *Journal of the West African College of Surgeons*, 8(4), 93–113.

Ganesh, A., Chaly, P. E., Reddy, V. C., Ingle, N. A., & Bhavyaa, R. (2019). Oral health awareness and oral hygiene status of 12-and 15-year-old children in Chennai. *Journal of Indian Association of Public Health Dentistry*, 17(3), 206-212.

Gautam, N., Kushwaha, A., Chandak, A., Yadav, Y., & Upadhyay, S. (2022). Oral Health Status among Children between the ages of 12 and 15 Attending Government and Private School Systems in Bareilly City. *Journal of Dental Science Research & Reports*, 4(3), 1-6.

Gebregiorgis, T. O., Humed, A. S., Tekle, B. M., Ghebremedhin, B. T., & Haile, L. H. (2021).

Level of Oral Hygiene Practices and its Association with Socio-Demographic Characters Among Middle School Students in Low-Income Countries. *Preprint (Version 1)*.

<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-627216/v1>

Ghanbari-Jahromi, M., Bastani, P., Jalali, F. S., & Delavari, S. (2023).

Factors affecting oral and dental services' utilization among Elderly: a scoping review. *BMC Oral Health*, 23(1), 597.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-023-03285-4>

Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. (2019).

Global Burden of Disease Study 2019 (GBD 2019). Seattle, United States of America: *Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME)*.

Goryawala, S. N. (2018). Vista of Oral Hygiene. In *Dental Caries-Diagnosis, Prevention and*

Management. IntechOpen. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.75382

Griehaber, A., Haschemi, A. A., Waltimo, T., Bornstein, M. M., & Kulik, E. M. (2022).

Caries status of first-born child is a predictor for caries experience in younger siblings. *Clinical Oral Investigations*, 26(1), 325-331.

Hakeem, K. R., Abdul, W. M., Hussain, M. M., Razvi, S. S. I., Hakeem, K. R., Abdul, W. M.,

... & Razvi, S. S. I. (2019). Oral hygiene for healthy life. *Oral Health and Herbal Medicine*, 5-6

Hanif, F., & Prasko, P. (2018). The difference of counselling with video media and hand puppets

to improving knowledge of dental and oral health in elementary school students. *Jurnal Kesehatan Gigi*, 5(2), 1-6.

Hu, X., Fan, X., Tian, J., Zhang, B., & Huang, R. (2023). Utilization of dental care service and associated factors among pre-school children in northwest China over the past decade. *BMC Oral Health*, 23(1), 1-6.

Igbinosa, L. O., Osisanya, M. O., Ojehanon, P. I., & Okeigbemen, S. A. (2018). Oral Health Status of 12-year-old Children in Public and. Private Schools in Benin City. *Nigerian Journal of Dental Research*, 3(1), 33-38.

Kuppuswamy, V. L., Murthy, S., Sharma, S., Surapaneni, K. M., Grover, A., & Joshi, A. (2014). Oral hygiene status, knowledge, perceptions and practices among school settings in rural South India. *Oral Health Dent Manag*, 13(1), 146-154.

Janani, K., Ganapathy, D., & Sasanka, K. (2022). Awareness Of Oral Hygiene Among Policemen in Mayiladuthurai. *JETT*, 13(6), 39-51.

Jibo, A. M., & Mubarak, M. T. (2018). Oral hygiene knowledge habits and practices among primary school pupils in Kano Nigeria. *Jos Journal of Medicine*, 12(2), 72-83.

Joyani, K. A., Heydarnia, A., & Zarei, F. (2018). Is peer education more effective than classical training for oral health behavior? *Journal of Health Literacy*, 3(3), 151-162.

Julihn, A., Soares, F. C., Hammarfjord, U., Hjern, A., & Dahllöf, G. (2020). Birth order is associated with caries development in young children: a register-based cohort study. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 218. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8234-7>

Kabir, M. N., Ahmed, M. B., & Khan, M. (2019). Knowledge and Oral Hygiene Practice by School Children in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. *Update Dental College Journal*, 9(2), 27-31.

Kalu, I. N., Agu, P. C., & Ukonu, C. C. (2020). Literature Review on Gender Differences in the Causes and Management of Work Stress. *Renaissance university journal of management and social sciences*, 6(1).

Kerr, R., Claman, D., Amini, H., Alexy, E., Kumar, A., & Casamassimo, P. S. (2019). Evaluation of the Ability of Five- to 11-Year-Olds to Brush Their Teeth Effectively with Manual and Electric Toothbrushing. *Pediatric dentistry*, 41(1), 20–24.

Kivelä, L., Papadopoulos, M. R., & Antypa, N. (2018). Chronotype and psychiatric disorders. *Current sleep medicine reports*, 4, 94-103.

Khalid, T., Mahdi, S. S., Khawaja, M., Allana, R., & Amenta, F. (2020). Relationship between socioeconomic inequalities and oral hygiene indicators in private and public schools in Karachi: An observational study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(23), 8893.

Lawal, F. B., Fagbule, O. F., Akinloye, S. J., Lawal, T. A., & Oke, G. A. (2022). Impact of oral hygiene habits on oral health-related quality of life of in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Frontiers in Oral Health*, 3, 979674. <https://doi.org/10.3389/froh.2022.979674>

Lebrun-Harris, L. A., Canto, M. T., & Vodicka, P. (2019). Preventive oral health care use and oral health status among US children: 2016 National Survey of Children’s Health. *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 150(4), 246-258.

Lucero, J. M., Vásquez Palacios, A. C., & Sacoto Figueroa, F. K. (2019). Oral hygiene index in 12-year-old schoolchildren of the Checa parish in Canton Cuenca, Province of Azuay, Ecuador, 2016. *Odontoestomatología*, 21(34), 27-32.

Maffioletti, F., Vettore, M. V., Rebelo, M., Herkrath, F., Queiroz, A., Herkrath, A. P., ... & Rebelo Vieira, J. (2020). Predisposing, enabling, and need characteristics of dental services utilization among socially deprived schoolchildren. *Journal of Public Health Dentistry*, 80(2), 97-106.

Mahboobi, Z., Pakdaman, A., Yazdani, R., Azadbakht, L., Shamsiri, A. R., & Babaei, A. (2021). Caries incidence of the first permanent molars according to the Caries Assessment Spectrum and Treatment (CAST) index and its determinants in children: a cohort study. *BMC Oral Health*, 21(1), 1-10.

Malhotra, D. S., Singh, D. P., Dubey, D. H., Jhunjhunwala, D. N., Chauhan, D. A., & Pandey, D. P. K. (2021). A cross-sectional study on the relationship between oral hygiene and socioeconomic status among 15-year-old school children. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(2), 1556-1564.

Mishra, P., Solanki, J., Choudhary, R., Sharma, C., Sharma, P., & Shah, D. (2019). Attitude towards oral hygiene among different socio-economic groups in Jaipur city, Rajasthan. *Medicine and Pharmacy Reports*, 92, 79 - 82.

Mohammed, H. M., Mehari, M. A., & Asgedom, A. A. (2023). Predictors of low dental service utilization among school children in Mekelle, Northern Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Oral Health*, 23(1), 41.

Mohammed, M., & Mohamed, Y. S. (2020). Birth order effect on oral health in a group of Egyptian children. *Egyptian Dental Journal*, 66(1-January (Orthodontics, Pediatric & Preventive Dentistry)), 35-40.

Monika, P., & Nikitha, S. (2022). Oral health practices among 10-15 years of government school children in Chengalpattu district, India: a cross-sectional survey. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 9(8), 3261.

Munawar, G.J., Triyanto, R., & Ambarwati, T. (2022). Knowledge and attitude of parents with dental hygiene of preschool children. *The Incisor (Indonesian Journal of Care's in Oral Health)*, 6 (2). pp. 447-455.

Nagarajappa, R., Naik, D., & Ramesh, G. (2021). Sources of oral health information and its relationship on knowledge among Indian adolescents. *Pesquisa Brasileira em Odontopediatria e Clínica Integrada*, 21, e0099. <https://doi.org/10.1590/pboci.2021.011>

Nagdev, P., Iyer, M. R., Naik, S., Khanagar, S. B., Awawdeh, M., Al Kheraif, A. A., ... & Alsadon, O. (2023). Andersen health care utilization model: A survey on factors affecting the utilization of dental health services among school children. *Plos one*, 18(6), e0286945.

Namdev, P., Goyal, S., Saxena, U., Gangil, K., Pathak, V., & Kushwah, A. (2021). A cross-sectional study to assess and compare the oral hygiene status, knowledge, and perceptions amongst the students studying in government and private schools of rural areas of Chambal region. *University Journal Of Dental Sciences*, 7(1).

Navarro-Carrillo, G., Alonso-Ferres, M., Moya, M., & Valor-Segura, I. (2020). Socioeconomic status and psychological well-being: Revisiting the role of subjective socioeconomic status. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1303.

Nepaul, P., & Mahomed, O. (2020). Influence of Parents' Oral Health Knowledge and Attitudes on Oral Health Practices of Children (5-12 Years) in a Rural School in KwaZulu-Natal, South

Africa. *Journal of International Society of Preventive & Community Dentistry*, 10(5), 605–612.

https://doi.org/10.4103/jispcd.JISPCD_273_20

New York State Department of Health. (2019). Infant and Children’s Oral Health. Retrieved November 11, 2023, from: https://www.health.ny.gov/prevention/dental/birth_oral_health.htm

Noh, E. M. (2020). The Relation Between Parenting Attitudes and Child’s Oral Health Behavior. *Journal of Convergence for Information Technology*, 10(12), 140-145.

Nottidge, T. E., Nottidge, B. A., & Ekrikpo, U. E. (2019). Prevalence and predictors of low back pain in a Southern Nigerian hospital. *Annals of African Medicine*, 18(3), 167–172. https://doi.org/10.4103/aam.aam_59_18

Nyatuka, B. O. (2020). Family-Community-Higher Education Partnership: A Critical Pillar in Realizing Social Justice. In *Handbook of Research on Diversity and Social Justice in Higher Education* (pp. 129-148). IGI Global.

Nzomiwu, C. L., Ayedun, O. S., & Orenuga, O. O. (2022). Oral Health Knowledge and Behavior among Public Primary Schoolchildren in Lagos, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*, 31(4), 383-389.

Ogordi, P. U., Osadolor, A. J., & Mohammed, B. I. (2022). Caries Risk Assessment among 6- to 12-Year-Old Public and Private School Children in Benin City, Nigeria—a pilot study. *Journal of Paediatric Dental Research and Practice*, 3(1&2), 1-8.

Okoli, S. C., Ogbalu, A. I., Ani, S. E., Nwosu, P. C., Enebechi, P. C., Hussein, B. M., & Omale, J. J. (2021). Prevalence of common oral diseases among Senior Secondary School students in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Orapuh Journal*, 2(3), e826-e826.

Olatosi, O. O., Oyapero, A., Onyejaka, N. K., & Boyede, G. O. (2020). Maternal knowledge, dental service utilization and self-reported oral hygiene practices in relation to oral health of preschool children in Lagos, Nigeria. *PAMJ-One Health*, 2(10).

Oliveira, S. C., Slot, D. E., & van der Weijden, F. (2014). Is it safe to use a toothbrush? *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica*, 72(8), 561–569.

Omorodion G, I., Osadolor A, J. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practices of dental patients presenting at a Secondary Health Care Facility in Southern Nigeria towards COVID-19. *Yenagoa Medical Journal*, 172-182.

Onigbinde O, O., Adenuga-Taiwo, A., Abah A, A., & Awotile O, A. (2020). Oral Health Behaviour and its Determinants among Dental, Medical and Nursing Students in a Tertiary Institution in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Saudi Journal of Oral and Dental Research*, 5(8), 387-393

Onyejaka, N. K., Uguru, N. P., & Uguru, C. C. (2020). Professional oral prophylaxis: Assessment of practice by oral health professionals in Southeastern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*, 29(4), 670-675.

Osadolor, O. O., & Iwuoha, C. E. (2019). Oral hygiene status of primary school children. *International Journal of Dentistry Research*, 4(3), 104-107

Osman, D. M., Edrees, M. F., Abdelrheem, S. S., & Abdelsalam, D. M. (2019). Oral health indices among secondary school students in Assiut governorate; upper Egypt. *Journal of High Institute of Public Health*, 49(3), 144-153.

Oyedele, T. A., Adeyemo, Y. I., Ladeji, A. M., Adetayo, A. M., & Nzomiwu, C. L. (2021). Comparison of Dental Caries and Oral Hygiene Status of Children in Suburban with those in Rural

Population of Southwestern Nigeria. *Pesquisa Brasileira em Odontopediatria e Clínica Integrada*, 21.

Oyedele, T. A., Folayan, M. O., Chukwumah, N. M., & Onyejaka, N. K. (2019). Social predictors of oral hygiene status in school children from suburban Nigeria. *Brazilian Oral Research*, 33, e022. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-3107bor-2019.vol33.0022>

Parveen, F., Afzal, M., Hussain, M., & Gilani, S. A. (2018). Knowledge, attitude and practice towards personal hygiene among primary: School children of rural area of Lahore, Pakistan. *Saudi J Nurs Health Care*, 1(3), 91-7.

Paul, S., & Rai, M. (2021). Role of the media. *Department of Peace and Conflict Studies and Management, Sikkim University, Gangtok, India. DOI*, 10, 978-3.

Pengpid, S., & Peltzer, K. (2020). Prevalence and Associated Factors of Hand and Oral Hygiene Behaviour among Adolescents in Dominican Republic, Suriname and Trinidad and Tobago. *Preprint*. doi: 10.20944/preprints202009.0711.v1

Peres, M. A., Macpherson, L. M. D., Weyant, R. J., Daly, B., Venturelli, R., Mathur, M. R., Listl, S., Celeste, R. K., Guarnizo-Herreño, C. C., Kearns, C., Benzian, H., Allison, P., & Watt, R. G. (2019). Oral diseases: a global public health challenge. *Lancet (London, England)*, 394(10194), 249–260. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)31146-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31146-8)

Pinge, S. D., More, S. G., Savant, S., Komble, R., & More, S. (2023). Assessment of Parents' Involvement and the Awareness of Oral Hygiene Practices among 10–12-Year-Old Schoolchildren in Pune City.

Portero de la Cruz, S., & Cebrino, J. (2020). Oral health problems and utilization of dental services among Spanish and immigrant children and adolescents. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(3), 738.

Pranno, N., Zumbo, G., Tranquilli, M., Stamegna, L., Zara, F., & Vozza, I. (2022). Oral Hygiene Habits and Use of Fluoride in Developmental Age: Role of Parents and Impact on their Children. *BioMed Research International*, 2022.

Pratamawari, D. N. P., Atikasari, D., & Bramantoro, T. (2022). The effect of parents' socioeconomic factors on their willingness to take care of their children's oral health in early childhood. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research*, 15(2), 845-849.

Punitha, V. C., & Sivaprakasam, P. (2011). Oral hygiene status, knowledge, attitude and practices of oral health among rural children of Kanchipuram district. *Indian Journal of Multidisciplinary Dentistry*, 1(2).

Rahman, M. M. (2023). Sample Size Determination for Survey Research and Non-Probability Sampling Techniques: A Review and Set of Recommendations. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economics*, 11(1), 42-62.

Rachmawati, Y. L., Rahardjo, A., & Maharani, D. A. (2018). Assessment of parents' and children's oral health-related behavior. *Journal of Stomatology*, 71(4), 344-349.

Rebelo, M. A. B., Rebelo Vieira, J. M., Pereira, J. V., Quadros, L. N., & Vettore, M. V. (2019). Does oral health influence school performance and school attendance? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International journal of paediatric dentistry*, 29(2), 138-148.

- Roudsari, M. S., Shariatpanahi, S. P., Namdari, M., Khoshnevisan, M. H., Malek-Mohamadi, M., & Foroughmand, M. H. (2021).** The role of peer influence on oral health knowledge and behaviors among adolescents. *Journal of Dentistry Indonesia*, 28 (1), 38-44.
- Saavedra, J. M., & Prentice, A. M. (2023).** Nutrition in school-age children: a rationale for revisiting priorities. *Nutrition Reviews*, 81(7), 823–843. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nutrit/nuac089>
- Sadana, P., Nagpal, M., & Kaur, S. (2020).** Awareness of Oral Hygiene among Government School Children in a Rural Area of Amritsar, Punjab—A Cross-sectional Study. *Annals of Community Health*, 8(2), 41-45.
- Salama, A. A., Konsowa, E. M., & Alkalash, S. H. (2020).** Mothers’ knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding their primary school children’s oral hygiene. *Menoufia Medical Journal*, 33(1), 11.
- Samuelsson, Y., & Samuelsson, E. (2018).** Oral Health and Tools for Oral Hygiene in Adolescents in Detema Secondary School. *Thesis*. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1274083/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Santoso, C. M. A., Bramantoro, T., Nguyen, M. C., & Nagy, A. (2021).** Lifestyle and psychosocial correlates of oral hygiene practice among Indonesian adolescents. *European Journal of Oral Sciences*, 129(1), e12755.
- Sarwer-Foner, S. N. D., Barasuol, J. C., & Vieira, R. S. (2021).** Impact of social media on the oral hygiene habits of children and adolescents: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *General Dentistry*, 69(1), 70-76.

Seidu, A. A., Amu, H., Salihu, T., Hagan Jr, J. E., Agbaglo, E., Amoah, A., ... & Ahinkorah, B. O. (2021). Prevalence and Factors Associated with Hygiene Behaviours among In-School Adolescents in Ghana. *J*, 4(2), 169-181.

Shalan, H. M., & Abo Bakr, R. (2018). Oral health status of preschool children in Egypt. *Acta Scientific Dental Sciences*, 2(5), 67-72.

Sharma, A. S., Sheth, S. A., Dhaduk, P. J., Chovateeya, S. R., Mistry, B. J., & Jogi, M. R. (2019). Oral hygiene practices and factors affecting oral health service utilization among children (11–14 years) of government school of nikol ward of East Zone of Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India. *Contemporary Clinical Dentistry*, 10(2), 299.

Shitu, K., Alemayehu, M., & Berassa, S. H. (2023). Oral hygiene behaviour and its determinants among preparatory school students in Gondar city, Northwest Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Dental Hygiene*.

Shomuyiwa, D. O., & Bridge, G. (2023). Oral health of adolescents in West Africa: prioritizing its social determinants. *Global Health Research and Policy*, 8(1), 1-9.

Singh, N., Gaur, S., Kumar, M., Chauhan, N.S., Akhtar, T., Agarwal, S., & Mathur, R. (2021). Comparative Study of Dental Health Status and Its Determinants among Children Attending Government and Private Schools in Kanpur City. *International Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*, 14, 666 - 673.

Singh, S., & Vijayakumar, N. (2020). Height and dental caries among 13-year-old adolescents in India: A sociobehavioral life course approach. *Dental Research Journal*, 17(5), 373.

Sony, S.A., Haseen, F., Islam, S.S., & Chowdhury, S.F. (2021). Knowledge and Practice of Oral Health and Hygiene and Oral Health Status among School Going Adolescents in a Rural Area of Sylhet District, Bangladesh. *Community Based Medical Journal*. 10(01), 30-36.

Souza, J. G. S., Sampaio, A. A., Costa Oliveira, B. E., Jones, K. M., & Martins, A. M. E. D. B. L. (2018). Socioeconomic inequalities in the use of dental care services during early childhood: an epidemiological survey. *International Journal of Paediatric Dentistry*, 28(4), 400-409.

Spadafora, N., Schiralli, K., & Al-Jbouri, E. (2019). Peer Groups. *Encyclopedia of Evolutionary Psychological Science*, 1-9.

Franz, J. (2018). Birth Order. *Gale Encyclopedia of Children's Health: Infancy through Adolescence*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/medicine/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/birth-order>

Tenny, S., Hoffman, M. R. (2023). *Prevalence*. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK430867/>

Teshome, A., Muche, A., & Girma, B. (2021). Prevalence of dental caries and associated factors in East Africa, 2000–2020: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 645091.

Trinh, V. A., Tarbit, E., Do, L., Ha, D., & Tadakamadla, S. K. (2021). The influence of family socioeconomic status on toothbrushing practices in Australian children. *Journal of Public Health Dentistry*, 81(4), 308-315.

Uguru, N., Onwujekwe, O., Ogu, U. U., & Uguru, C. (2020). Access to Oral health care: a focus on dental caries treatment provision in Enugu Nigeria. *BMC Oral Health*, 20(1), 1-13.

Ulloa, S. L., Vélez, E. L., Jara, F. C., & Carrera, K. C. (2020). Oral hygiene in schools of 6 years of age of the Baños Rural Parish - Ecuador. *Revista KIRU*, 17(1), 10-15.
<https://doi.org/10.24265/kiru.2020.v17n1.02>

Valm A. M. (2019). The Structure of Dental Plaque Microbial Communities in the Transition from Health to Dental Caries and Periodontal Disease. *Journal of molecular biology*, 431(16), 2957–2969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2019.05.016>

Xu, X., Zhou, Y., Liu, C., Zhao, L., Zhang, L., Li, H., ... & Cheng, X. (2023). Effects of water flossing on gingival inflammation and supragingival plaque microbiota: a 12-week randomized controlled trial. *Clinical Oral Investigations*, 1-11.

Yeo, K. Y., Hashimoto, K., Archer, T., Kenny, K., Pavitt, S., & Zoltie, T. (2020). Evaluation of the effectiveness of a peer-led video on oral hygiene education in young children. *Journal of Visual Communication in Medicine*, 43(3), 119-127.

Zambaldi, M. P. M., Molina, M. D. C. B., Martinelli, K. G., & Santos-Neto, E. T. D. (2022). Children, maternal and socioeconomic characteristics influence oral hygiene habits in schoolchildren. *Journal of Human Growth and Development*, 32(2), 202-213.

Zikri, Z., Yuliati, L. N., & Simanjuntak, M. (2019). The Influence of Socialization Agents and TV Advertising on Attitudes and Behaviors of Toothbrushing in Elementary School Students. *Jurnal Ilmu Keluarga & Konsumen*, 12(2), 169-180.

APPENDIX I: CONSENT FORM

Title of study: **Assessment of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State.**

Principal Investigator: OSADOLOR, Aisosa Junior

Institution: National Open University of Nigeria, Benin City, Nigeria.

Contact Information: aise.osadolor@outlook.com 07013919301

Introduction

Your child is being invited to participate in a research study titled ‘Assessment of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State’ at various public and private primary schools in Benin City. This study aims to gain insights into the predictors of oral hygiene practices such as toothbrushing and the use of dental floss among schoolchildren. Your child’s participation in this study is voluntary.

Study Procedures

Suppose you consent to your child’s participation, and your child gives assent to participate on the study day. In that case, we will complete a questionnaire that consists of questions about your child’s oral hygiene habits. The questionnaire is designed to protect your child’s anonymity, and their responses will be kept confidential.

Benefits of Participation

Participants will be instructed on the appropriate time for toothbrushing, how to brush their teeth [hands-on practical session], when to see a dentist, and what tooth-cleaning products to use.

Risks of Participation

There are no risks associated with your child participating in this study.

Confidentiality

Your child’s participation and responses will be kept strictly confidential. Your identity will be anonymized, and the data will be reported in aggregate form. Only the research team will have access to the collected data.

Voluntary Participation

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. Your child can decline participation or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits.

Contact Information

If you have any questions or concerns about the study, contact OSADOLOR, Aisosa Junior, at aise.osadolor@outlook.com. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, you can contact the Health Research Ethics Committee at the Edo State Ministry of Health.

Consent

I have read and understood the above information about the study ‘Assessment of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State’. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and have received satisfactory answers. I understand that my child’s participation is voluntary, and my child can withdraw at any time without consequence. I consent to my child’s participation in this study.

Parent/Guardian’s Signature

Date

Participant’s Signature/Thumbprint

Date

APPENDIX II: QUESTIONNAIRE

Assessment of the predictors of oral hygiene habits among schoolchildren in Benin City.

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Age _____

Gender: Male Female

Father's level of education _____

Mother's level of education _____

Father's occupation _____

Mother's occupation _____

Birth rank _____

Family size _____

Family composition

School type Public Private

- i. Father and Mother
- ii. Mother only
- iii. Father only
- iv. Guardian
- v. Others: _____

QUESTIONS ON ORAL HYGIENE PRACTICE

1. Do you brush your teeth daily? Yes No
2. If Yes or No in item 1 above, how many times do you brush in a day whenever you brush?

 - i. When, in relation to meals, do you do it? _____
 - ii. For how long (in minutes) do you brush your teeth? _____
3. What do you use to brush your teeth?
 - i. Toothpaste and toothbrush
 - ii. Chewing stick
 - iii. Charcoal
 - iv. Salt and water
 - v. Others: _____
4. If applicable, from whom or where did you learn:
 - i. How to use what you use to brush your teeth _____
5. Do you clean in between your teeth? Yes No
 - i. What do you use to clean in between your teeth? _____
6. If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to use dental floss, toothpick, or thread? _____
7. Have your teachers taught you about how to keep your teeth clean? Yes No

Assessing the Predictors of Oral Hygiene Habits Among Schoolchildren

8. Do you brush your teeth after eating snacks? Yes No
9. Do you know what a mouthwash is? Yes No
10. Do you use a mouthwash? Yes No
11. If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to brush your teeth after eating snacks? _____
12. If applicable, from whom or where did you learn how to use mouthwash? _____
13. What type (strength) of toothbrush do you use?
 - i. Hard bristle strength
 - ii. Medium bristle strength
 - iii. Soft bristle strength
14. Who (or what) advised the use of your current toothbrush? _____
15. How often in a year do you change your toothbrush? _____
16. Concerning item 15, from whom/where did you adopt the duration of changing your toothbrush? _____
17. Have you had at least one dental visit within the following timeframes:
 - i. Last one year _____
 - ii. Last three years _____
 - iii. Last five years _____
 - iv. Since birth _____
 - v. Had never visited _____
18. What do you think will happen to your teeth if you do not brush your teeth often?

19. Has anyone close to you ever praised or scolded you for brushing/not brushing your teeth regularly? _____
Who did? _____

APPENDIX III: RELIABILITY TEST-RETEST STATISTIC SUMMARY

Test-retest reliability statistics, including items 1 to 19; SPSS output presented below:

**Oral hygiene habit_Questionnaire test 1 * Oral hygiene habit_Questionnaire test 2
Crosstabulation**

		Oral hygiene habit_Questionnaire Retest			Total
		Poor oral hygiene habit	Fair oral hygiene habit	Good oral hygiene habit	
Oral hygiene habit_Questionnaire Test	Poor oral hygiene habit	5	3	0	8
	Fair oral hygiene habit	0	10	0	10
	Good oral hygiene habit	0	0	2	2
Total		5	13	2	20

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Measure of Agreement	Kappa	.735	.140	4.333	.000
N of Valid Cases		20			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

**APPENDIX IV: STATE UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION BOARDS' APPROVAL
LETTER**

EDO STATE UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION BOARD (SUBEB)

Our Ref: SUBEB/A/3007T/2

February 12, 2024

Osadolor Aisosa Jr.
Public Health Sciences,
Faculty of Sciences
National Open University, Benin Study Centre
Edo State.

Dear Sir,

APPROVAL LETTER

Your letter dated 20th December, 2023 requesting for ethical permit refers.

2. Following interactions between you and the Board, I am directed to provide you with relevant information as follows:
3. The postgraduate research project titled, "Assessment of the Predictors of Oral hygiene habits among Schoolchildren in Benin City, Edo State." The research will be conducted among primary six pupils in the following public primary schools in Oredo (Uvbi and Uwa P/S) and Egor (Evbotubu and Egor P/S) which will commence from Monday 19th February to 26th February 2024.
4. The research will be done during the break period in four primary schools whose relevant data is attached to this letter.
5. It is expected that the information supplied will only be used for research purposes as requested. Any other use of data supplied other than the above must get express authorization from the Board.
6. Please, accept the highest regards of the Executive Chairman.

Uhunmwangho J. Imariabe,
Director, Social Mobilization
For: The Executive Chairman

APPENDIX V: ETHICAL APPROVAL CERTIFICATE

EDO STATE MINISTRY OF HEALTH
HEALTH RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

PROTOCOL NUMBER HA/737/24/C/02060211(PLEASE QUOTE IN ALL ENQUIRIES)
TITLE OF RESEARCH PROPOSAL ASSESSMENT OF THE PREDICTORS OF ORAL HYGIENE HABITS AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN IN BENIN CITY, EDO STATE.
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (S) OSADOLOR, AISOSA JUNIOR
DATE CONSIDERED 06thFEBRUARY, 2024
DECISION OF THE COMMITTEE APPROVED

THIS APPROVAL DATES 06/02/2024 TO 06/02/2025. IF THERE IS A DELAY IN STARTING THE RESEARCH, PLEASE INFORM THE HREC EDO SMoH SO THAT THE DATES OF APPROVAL CAN BE ADJUSTED ACCORDINGLY

REMARK: Please kindly note that the HREC Edo SMoH seal authenticates this approval

DR (MRS) Omonyemen B. BELLO
(MBBS, MPH, FPHCM) (CHAIRMAN)

SIGNATURE & DATE.....

Signature
6/2/24

SUPERVISOR(S)

ATTESTATION BY INVESTIGATOR(S)

No participant accrual or activity related to this research may be conducted outside of the approval dates. All informed consent forms used in this study must carry the Edo SMoH HREC-assigned number and duration of your research. No changes are permitted in the research without prior approval of the Edo SMoH HREC except in circumstances outlined in the Code. The Edo SMoH HREC reserves the right to conduct compliance visits to your research site without previous notification.

Signature & Date.....

Signature
7/2/2024